

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D7.1: 1st Dissemination Plan

WP7 – Dissemination

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	649493	Acronym	STEP	
Full Project Title	Societal and political engagement of young people in environmental issues			
Start Date	1 st June 2015	Duration	30 months	
Project URL	www.step4youth.eu			
Deliverable	D 7.1 – 1 st Dissemination Plan			
Work Package	WP 7 - Dissemination			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	31 August 2015	Actual	31 August 2015
Nature	R - Report	Dissemination Level	P – Public	
Lead Beneficiary	DRAXIS Environmental S.A.			
Responsible Author	Ms Panagiota Syropoulou (DRAXIS) Mr. Lazaros Xenidis (DRAXIS) Ms. Ioanna Papaioannou (DRAXIS) Mr. Vassilis Tsekeridis (DRAXIS)			
Contributions from	Ms. Sinem Sadıkoğlu (HATAY) Ms. Anna Kagiampaki (ROC) Mr. Gonzalo Martin (VALD) Mr. Francesco Mollace (CSB) Mr. Albert Garcia Macian (MDV) Dr. Reinhard Busch (LINGUATEC)			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1.0	20/7/2015	Draft		
2.0	10/8/2015	Draft	Contribution from pilot partners	Ms. Sinem Sadıkoğlu Ms. Anna Kagiampaki Mr. Gonzalo Martin Mr. Francesco Mollace Mr. Albert Garcia Macian
3.0	31/8/2015	Final	Review	Dr. Reinhard Busch (LINGUATEC)

Disclaimer

The present Deliverable reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© STEP Consortium, 2015

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Contents

1	Executive summary	6
2	Context.....	6
3	STEP Dissemination Strategy.....	7
3.1	Objectives	7
3.2	Target Audiences	8
3.3	Expected Results	10
4	Dissemination tools.....	10
4.1	Project visual identity (logo) and slogan	10
4.2	Dissemination templates	11
4.3	Project website	13
4.4	STEP QR Code.....	14
4.5	E-mail account and mailing lists	14
4.6	Social media	15
4.6.1	Facebook page	15
4.6.2	Twitter account.....	16
4.6.3	LinkedIn group	16
4.6.4	Google+ page	16
4.7	Audiovisual material – YouTube channel	17
4.8	Newsletters.....	17
4.9	Factsheet	18
4.10	Press releases.....	18
4.11	Brochure, leaflet, and poster	18
4.12	Project communication kit.....	19
4.13	Other dissemination material	19
5	Dissemination activities	19
5.1	Network of Interest.....	19
5.2	Mass media communication	20
5.3	Press releases.....	20
5.4	Publications.....	21
5.5	Posts in non-project channels.....	21
5.6	Participation in targeted events.....	22
5.6.1	Scientific conferences	22

5.6.2	Workshops, road shows, TEDx events.....	23
5.6.3	Open events.....	23
5.7	Organisation of project events.....	24
5.8	Informal person-to-person meetings.....	24
5.9	Online/ mobile games & applications	25
5.10	Collaboration with similar projects/ initiatives	25
6	Internal dissemination	27
6.1	Document sharing.....	27
6.2	E-mail communication	27
7	Strengths and responsibilities of the project partners.....	28
8	Monitoring, Reporting & Evaluation	29
9	Dissemination impact indicators.....	31
10	Timeplan for the first year of the project.....	32
11	Conclusions.....	34
ANNEX A-PROJECT PARTNERS.....		35
A.1	DRAXIS ENVIRONMENTAL S.A. (DRAXIS)	35
A.2	CENTRE FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY HELLAS (CERTH)	35
A.3	LINGUATEC GMBH (LINGUATEC) GMBH	35
A.4	THE UNIVERSITY COURT OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ABERTAY DUNDEE (ABERTAY).....	35
A.5	INMARK ESTUDIOS Y ESTRATEGIAS SA (INMARK)	36
A.6	REGION OF CRETE (ROC).....	36
A.7	SAMPAS BILISIM VE ILETISIM SISTEMLERI SANAYI VE TICARET A.S. (SAMPAS)	36
A.8	HATAY METROPOLITAN MUNICIPALITY (HATAY)	37
A.9	COMUNE DI SANT'AGATA DEL BIANCO (CSB)	37
A.10	YEE-YOUTH AND ENVIRONMENT EUROPE (YEE).....	37
A.11	AJUNTAMENT DE MOLLET DEL VALLES (MDV)	38
A.12	KAIROS FUTURE AKTIEBOLAG (KAIROS).....	38
A.13	AYUNTAMIENTO DE VALDEMORO (VALD).....	38
ANNEX B – LOCAL DISSEMINATION STRATEGIES		39
B.0	Local Dissemination Strategy Outline	39
B.0.1	Local Dissemination Strategy phases	39
B.0.2	Communication activities.....	42
B.0.3	Measurement of success	45
B.0.3	Collecting Requirements.....	45
B.0.4	Stakeholders management	46

B.1 Context of the dissemination activities in Italy (Comune Di Sant’ Agata del Bianco).....	48
B.1.1 Current situation.....	48
B.1.2 Target audiences.....	49
B.1.3 Specialisation of the strategy.....	51
B.2 Context of the dissemination activities in Spain (Mollet de Valles Municipality & Valdemoro Municipality).....	51
B.2.1 Current situation.....	51
B.2.2 Target audiences.....	52
B.2.3 Specialisation of the strategy.....	55
B.3 Context of the dissemination activities in Greece (Region of Crete).....	56
B.3.1 Current situation.....	56
B.3.2 Target audiences.....	57
B.3.3 Specialisation of the strategy.....	59
B.4 Context to the dissemination activities in Turkey (Hatay Metropolitan Municipality).....	59
B.4.1 Current situation.....	59
B.4.2 Target audiences.....	60
B.4.3 Specialisation of the strategy.....	61
ANNEX C – NEWSLETTER TEMPLATE.....	63
ANNEX D – STEP LEAFLET.....	64
ANNEX E –MASS MEDIA & NEWS AGENCIES.....	64
ANNEX F – RELEVANT JOURNALS.....	66
ANNEX G – TARGETED EVENTS.....	67
ANNEX H – REPORTING TEMPLATES.....	70
H1 Template for Reporting Dissemination Publications.....	70
H2 Template for Reporting Dissemination Events.....	70

Table of Figures

Figure 1: The STEP Logo.....	10
Figure 2: EU emblem.....	11
Figure 3: Banner for the STEP Facebook page.....	11
Figure 4: STEP deliverables’ template.....	12
Figure 5: STEP presentation template.....	13
Figure 6: Local Dissemination Strategy phases.....	41

1 Executive summary

The purpose of the Dissemination Plan is to set the dissemination strategy that will be followed and elaborate the project's dissemination activities that will be executed throughout the duration of the project.

Dissemination and stakeholder engagement is crucial to the success of STEP. This document provides a description of the STEP dissemination strategy and elaborates how this strategy will be locally applied to the pilot areas. The STEP consortium recognises that dissemination activities are an essential and pervasive activity throughout the project's life, and thus they will be integrated within all its work packages.

This dissemination strategy describes the project's dissemination objectives and measures for achieving them throughout the duration of the project. It defines and prioritises the key objectives of the project's dissemination, identifies the main target groups and the reasons for which we want to reach them, and sets the expected results (Chapter 3). Moreover, it identifies and prioritises dissemination tools (Chapter 4) and activities (Chapter 5), elaborates the procedures of monitoring the dissemination impact (Chapter 8 & 9), and defines timelines for the planned dissemination activities for the first year of the project (Chapter 10).

This Dissemination Plan will be revised in May 2016. Annual reports on the activities of the Network of Interest and other Dissemination Activities will serve to monitor progress and inform the revision of the Dissemination Strategy.

2 Context

Promoting youth participation in environmental decision making is fundamental in the EU policy. However, half of the young people tend to distrust the European Union as they feel that their opinions are not heard. STEP addresses the need of public organisations to effectively open their decision-making procedures that have an environmental impact to young people, using a multi-disciplinary and balanced approach combining ICT and Social Sciences cutting-edge technologies and methods. The overall objective of the project is to develop and pilot test a cloud eParticipation SaaS platform, (available as both a mobile application and a web platform) enhanced with web / social media mining, gamification, machine translation, and visualisation features, which will promote the societal and political participation of young people in the decision-making process on environmental issues.

During the project, the STEP cloud eParticipation SaaS platform will be developed and pilot tested in five pilot communities with the direct participation of one regional authority, three municipalities, and one association of municipalities. The project will be implemented through the achievement of the following specific objectives:

- To enable public authorities to quickly open their decision-making processes to young people
- To enable young citizens to participate in decision-making on issues with environmental impact
- To develop engagement and motivation strategies for increasing youth participation in environmental decision making
- To pilot test the services in an operational environment in terms of technical, organisational and legal feasibility, with the participation of end users (young citizens) and policy makers

- To assess the usability, effectiveness and impact of the project in embedding open engagement in public sector processes, and identify the key barriers for wide scale deployment
- To ensure appropriate (state of the art) dissemination and realistic exploitation of project activities and results.

Under the scope of the main objective of STEP to enable and encourage the participation of young people in decision-making processes on environmental issues, one of the main elements crucial for the successful implementation of the project and the sustainability of its main outcomes is the maximised participation of the targeted group of young people and other potential stakeholders. Successful pilot installations are a precondition for the sustainability of the STEP solution as they will serve as ambassadors and examples for future users.

3 STEP Dissemination Strategy

3.1 Objectives

One of the main elements crucial for the successful implementation of the STEP project and the sustainability of its main outcomes is the maximised participation of young people and other target groups.

The main objectives of the STEP dissemination activities are to:

- Raise awareness of the youth community (youth organisations, bodies and organisations in the field of youth, formal, informal and non-formal education and training organisations, young people in general). Achieve diversity and inclusiveness by involving a demographically balanced group of young people reflecting the community and the community needs.
- Raise awareness of local, regional and national policy makers and public bodies, especially in the field of environment
- Maximise participation in operations offered by the developed platform/ mobile app through the project by drawing attention of young people with the use of targeted communication means, integrated in common interaction contexts, such as education, information, entertainment and social networking
- Ensure efficient communication and understanding regarding the project, obtain support and encourage participation of all stakeholders involved, as well as the wide public in disseminating information and exploiting results
- Introduce new patterns of conduct in the target groups – the end users of the project's main outputs and results
- Integrate targeted approaches, eliciting enhanced networking to disseminate new and sustainable ideas, with the use of innovative and creative means
- Establish formal and non-formal networks, also strengthening and valorising existing ones, for the exchanging of ideas and practices, in order to develop the sense of a community in participating in decision making in the fields of environment and sustainable development and the public sphere in general.

Thus, the dissemination strategy aims to engage all stakeholders involved in environmental policy in a positive interaction, harnessing global experience from experts and local experience from participatory events.

3.2 Target Audiences

STEP's dissemination activities will ensure the wide reaching impact and uptake of the platform among the following stakeholders:

- Young men and women all over Europe belonging to the age range 18-29, but also to other ages. Particular focus will be also paid on including young people with fewer opportunities, such as people who are not familiar with the use of digital tools and/or who have no internet access. With STEP, this target group will be better informed about environmental issues in local, national, and global level, will be able to voice their opinions, and connect with others around shared interests.
- Local, regional and national authorities all over Europe. The potential interest of this target group for the STEP project stems from their need to increase transparency and accountability of public organisations, and to reduce costs and rationalise resources.
- Local, regional and national stakeholders involved in the decision making procedures for youth and environment. Using the STEP platform, these stakeholders will be able to redesign service delivery on the principles of openness and youth participation, strengthen organisational capacity in managing the eParticipation procedure, and increase efficiency and quality of policy development.
- NGOs active in the fields of political and social participation, environment and youth issues. Participating in the STEP project, NGOs will be able to further motivate their members to be active in issues relevant to environment and youth participation, as well as they will have the potential to attract and engage new members.
- Project partners; partners' staff who will act as members of the Executive Board and the General Assembly, as well as members of the working groups of the project. Project partners are interested to successfully realise the project objectives and achieve exploitable results.
- The general public. The potential interest of the general public to participate in the STEP project derives from their need to be better informed about environmental issues and be involved in decision-making procedures for topics of their interest.

Different approaches are being developed to achieve:

- Support for the aims and objectives of the project to motivate target audience to act
- Participation in training events by the defined target groups by directly addressing them
- General awareness on the topic of youth participation in decision making on environmental issues using existing communities and networks.

In the first phase of the STEP dissemination process, representatives of the project partners will act as the dissemination channel that will ensure the commitment of experts of related fields with high-level of knowledge and experience in policy making and environmental issues. The objective is to form a Network of Interest in order to act as a main dissemination pole for other stakeholders. In the next phase, representatives of NGOs and networks with in-depth knowledge in decision making procedures for youth and environment, local and regional authorities all over Europe, and local and regional stakeholders involved in the decision making procedures for youth and environment will organise jointly with the project partners a set of participatory events in order to ensure the participation of young men and women. Young people all over Europe is the target group that is considered as the end users of the STEP platform, and, thus, they will be particularly motivated to participate actively in the activities of the project in order to communicate their own message to the parties concerned (local and regional authorities, policy making bodies, etc.). At the same time, the results of the participatory events will provide useful experience for experts in order to expand and assess the current knowledge and disseminate the project's outcomes. Finally, project partners, local and regional stakeholders, representatives of NGOs and young participants will exploit the experience

D7.1: 1st Dissemination Plan

gained from the dissemination activities as a means of creating a positive pressure stream towards local and regional authorities and stakeholders concerned with policy making.

The following table summarises the main target groups, and why we want to reach them.

Target group	Why we want to reach them
Young people	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To directly engage them in the project • To inform them about the potential benefits from their participation in project activities • To integrate their perspectives in the platform design
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local, regional and national authorities • Local, regional and national stakeholders involved in the decision making procedures for youth and environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To integrate their perspectives in the platform design • To inform them about the potential benefits from their participation in project activities • To engage them in training activities
NGOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To encourage them to raise awareness of their members about the project and its activities and results • To gain their insight and learn from their experiences in similar initiatives • To exchange information and views • To seek ways of collaboration, so as to maximise efficiency of the project activities, and achieve wider visibility
Project partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To ensure the commitment of experts of related fields and form a Network of Interest • To spread information about the project to their members/ customers/ contacts
General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To directly engage them in the project • To integrate their perspectives in the platform design • To inform them about the potential benefits from their participation in project activities • To achieve better visibility of the project activities

The detailed outline of the dissemination streams is presented in ANNEX B – LOCAL DISSEMINATION STRATEGIES.

3.3 Expected Results

The expected results of the STEP dissemination strategy are:

- The awareness raising about the project activities, informing the target audiences and the general public about the existence of the STEP project. This will be done mainly during the initial stage of the project and actively supported by the dissemination tools. However, also during the whole lifetime of STEP, the consortium will create publicity of the project to attract potential future stakeholders and ensure maximum impact.
- The explanation to the target groups which benefits the project provides and how the results can be exploited.
- The promotion of active participation in the project, e.g. via the attendance in the project workshops enhancing the links to other projects and stimulating the participation in the STEP External Expert Advisory Board. This will be done to promote the take up of the STEP platform by an increasing number of local authorities and young people.

4 Dissemination tools

The following sections describe the dissemination tools that will be used within the context of the STEP dissemination activities. These tools will be further specified after consultation with local partners and in relevance to the specified priorities on local level.

4.1 Project visual identity (logo) and slogan

The logo is the main graphic identity element of the project and the key to build a successful graphic identity as well as an effective logotype. The logo will be used in dissemination material and documents related to the project.

The logo chosen (Figure 1) is clear, captures the attention of the public and communicates the main concepts of STEP. Two versions have been developed: The first version displays the project's acronym in a single font, in conjunction with speech bubbles in various vivid colours that capture the attention of youth and indicate the variety of opinions that will be brought together through the STEP platform. The second version is accompanied by the project's full title in a smaller font size. The first logo will be used mainly for the internal communication, such as the project's deliverables, while the second logo will be used for other dissemination activities.

Figure 1: The STEP Logo

All dissemination material of STEP will include the STEP logo, the EU emblem, and a clear statement that the project has received funding from the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

A copy of the EU emblem and a text stating that the project has received funding from the Horizon 2020 programme will be included in any dissemination material including the electronic ones. This emblem is available from the EU at the link: <http://europa.eu/about-eu/basic-information/symbols/flag/>. The EU emblem accompanied by the abovementioned text will be added as follows:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493.

Figure 2: EU emblem

In order to transmit a coherent message towards the target groups, STEP will be linked with a catchy slogan as a mean to draw attentions. All STEP partners agreed that this slogan will be: “One STEP closer to participation”.

Moreover, various online and offline project banners will be created in order to enhance the graphical identity of the project and facilitate the communication of the main ideas of the project. The banners will be developed based on feedback from young people so they are suitable to generate awareness, raise curiousness and motivate them to participate in the project activities.

It is envisioned to use these banners on the project's website, newsletters, leaflets, social media accounts, etc. For instance, the project banner that will be used for the STEP Facebook page is presented below.

Figure 3: Banner for the STEP Facebook page

4.2 Dissemination templates

All reports, presentations, press releases and other printed dissemination material will use the prepared STEP templates in order to follow the overall graphical identity of the project. These templates will be shared among partners through a means that will be agreed.

Deliverables' template

For the needs of the preparation of the project's deliverables, a deliverable template has been produced in an MS Word format using a certain style. The purpose of such a template is to have a consistent and recognisable layout for the project's deliverables. The deliverable template has a cover page that displays the project's logo in a prominent position, the name of the deliverable and the relevant Work Package, while at the bottom of the page there is a clear statement that the project has received funding from the EU along with the emblem of the EU as required in the Article 29.4 of the Grant Agreement.

The second page of the template includes a table with the document's information and a table with the document history. Moreover, it contains a disclaimer that excludes the responsibility of the European Commission for any use that may be made of the information contained in any deliverable as required by Grant Agreement Article 29.5. In the same page a copyright message is displayed in order to protect the originality of any produced content within the STEP project.

The third page of the deliverable template is reserved for the tables of contents and figures. The first, second, and third page of the template remain static, do not change and contain only the information referred above. The footer of the template also contains the EU emblem and the project logo.

Figure 4: STEP deliverables' template

Presentation template

The STEP presentations are part of the different dissemination tools designed to support the STEP dissemination efforts. The presentation template will be used in all events and meetings where STEP results and activities are presented and it was designed following the graphic identity guidelines to facilitate the recognition of the project.

The project presentation template is presented in Figure 5. The STEP and the European logo have also been added in each one slide.

Figure 5: STEP presentation template

4.3 Project website

The goal of the project's website is to be used as the main tool to disseminate the project objectives and results to the target groups and the general public. In more detail, the STEP website will provide updated information on the following topics:

- Project overview
 - The STEP general concept and objectives
 - Basic information about the STEP platform (architecture and components, technical requirements, activities)
- Information of the project partners and links to the partners' websites
- Presentation of the members of the STEP External Expert Advisory Board
- Description of the pilot areas where STEP will be tested
- Public outcomes, such as
 - Public deliverables
 - Presentations
 - Fact sheets
 - Manuscripts published in journals
 - Abstracts and articles from conference proceedings and press releases etc.
- Information and links to similar projects/initiatives

- A newsfeed with the latest news about STEP relevant topics
- Basic information on internal and external events and activities and photos from the events
- Link to the STEP e-participation platform
- Social media links (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Google+, YouTube)

The STEP website will be available at www.step4youth.eu. It will be designed taking into account specific provisions and requirements related to obligations to the EU, gender issues and target groups/stakeholders., while it will be available in English.

Partners are committed to add a link to the STEP website in their organisation's websites, social networks, blogs, fora, and portals or even their personal networks in order to promote on a regular basis the STEP project. Requests will be also made to include a link to the STEP website on the relevant public authorities' websites of the countries where the pilot sites are located and on websites of Youth Councils and Youth Associations, Environmental NGOs and other stakeholder organisations.

Throughout the duration of the project, the website will be constantly updated while additional sections may be added. The website traffic will be monitored using Google analytics, a tool that helps to analyse visitor traffic and gives a complete picture of the website audience and their needs. Google analytics will be used in order to improve the website quality and to evaluate the website use as a dissemination tool.

4.4 STEP QR Code

A QR code will be created in order to allow mobile users to quickly access STEP information and webpage, and to download the eParticipation application to their mobile devices. The QR code will be included in different types of dissemination material, such as printed leaflets and posters, in order to raise public awareness on the project and increase user engagement.

4.5 E-mail account and mailing lists

An e-mail account which the public will be able to address for any issue relevant to the STEP project has been created: info@step4youth.eu. This account will be included in all used dissemination tools, such as the project website, social media accounts, printed material etc. DRAXIS, as the coordinator of the project, will be responsible for the administration of this account, while enquiries, comments, and information will be forwarded by DRAXIS to project partners if necessary.

Regarding the mailing lists, one list will be created containing e-mail addresses from partners' contacts and other people whom we will identify as important. These people may be associate partners, targeted stakeholders, young people with interests in the project, and potential STEP users. As the project evolves, this list will be enriched with interested stakeholders that are subscribed to the newsletter through the project website. Invitations to project events, project updates and electronic copies of the STEP newsletters will be sent to this list so that the STEP consortium keeps contact with this community throughout the duration of the project.

A second mailing list containing the e-mail addresses of all STEP partners has already been created. This list will be used for the internal communication between partners, for example in order to send requests for feedback and communicate project progress.

Both STEP mailing lists will be managed by DRAXIS, while all partners are committed to send DRAXIS any material that should be distributed to these lists.

4.6 Social media

Social networks have become major communication hubs and will be especially taken into account in the face of active and vivid user engagement efforts of the STEP project. Therefore a STEP Facebook page, a Twitter account, a LinkedIn group, a Google+ page, and a YouTube channel will be created, and will be linked to the project's website. The project partners are envisioned to upload all project-related important information to the social networks under the permission of WP7 leader¹ in order to support the dissemination efforts. More details about the social networks are presented below.

4.6.1 Facebook page

The STEP Facebook page will be created in a public mode with the name "STEP H2020 Project". The official language of the posts uploaded to this page will be English. However, other languages can also be used by partners, especially the ones from the pilot countries.

The WP7 leader will be the administrator of the Facebook page. The administrator's role is to manage all aspects of the page including messages dispatch and publication of posts, confirmation of posts and comments, assignment of page roles. DRAXIS as the coordinator of the project will be added as an editor of the page. Moreover, bearing in mind that partner YEE has the potential to promote the page to a wide network of young people, it will also be added as an editor. The editor has the same roles with the administrator except for assigning Facebook page roles. Additional editors may be added during the development of the project.

The page will be open to everyone to follow. However, the preferred audience has been defined as follows:

- Locations: pilot sites
- Age range: 18-29
- Gender: all
- Preferred Interests:
 - Topic: Hobbies and activities
 - Keywords: Politics and social issues, Community issues, Environmentalism, Sustainability, Sustainability development, Green politics etc.

A brief description of the project will be added to the STEP Facebook page in order to inform the general public about the objectives of the project. The links to the STEP website and the STEP platform will be also displayed in the STEP Facebook page.

The page will be shared to various directions in order to maximise its popularity. More specifically, it will be shared to:

- Targeted Facebook groups such as:
 - Local, regional and national authorities and public organisations, mainly from the pilot sites
 - Local, regional and national stakeholders involved in the decision making procedures for youth and environment
 - NGOs active in the fields of political and social participation, environment, youth and gender issues

¹ An amendment for the change of the WP7 leader is in progress.

- Youth associations
- Similar EU funded projects
- Other Facebook pages that project partners manage
- Partners' Facebook accounts etc.

Pilot partners will be asked to take advantage of the dissemination channels to which they have access, such as Municipalities' Facebook pages or accounts, in order to raise awareness at local/ regional level in areas where user engagement is a priority.

4.6.2 *Twitter account*

The STEP Twitter account will be used as a primary tool in spreading the projects' news and announcements. In the Twitter account, tweets will be uploaded in a regular base, referring to STEP results and news, and any important information that is relevant to the STEP objectives. The STEP Twitter account will be a useful channel to immediately disseminate project activities and news to a wide audience.

The account's editorial control belongs to the WP7 leader. However, each project partner, as well as each Twitter user, will be able to add links to announcements using the STEP hashtag and make retweets.

STEP twitter account: @STEP_H2020

Preferred hashtag for project tweets: #STEP_H2020

4.6.3 *LinkedIn group*

A STEP LinkedIn group will be created and managed by the WP7 leader. LinkedIn is a business-oriented social networking service and differs from other social media since it is mostly used for professional reasons. The LinkedIn group will be used for building up a professional network with experts and groups of experts. The initial target audience includes professionals, partners' LinkedIn circles, regional and community organisations staff and policy makers, entrepreneurs, etc. As the STEP LinkedIn group matures throughout the duration of the project, it will be used as a mechanism for spreading news of interest (updates, photos and posts) to group-members. The official language of the group will be English. Any LinkedIn member may join this group after the approval of the administrator (Members-only group).

The STEP LinkedIn group name is "STEP H2020 project".

The account's editorial control belongs to the leader of WP7. However, the project partners have the right to ask for access to the account.

4.6.4 *Google+ page*

A Google+ page will be established in order to provide a clear central profile to associate with the STEP YouTube presence and any further Google tools which will be adopted. A link will be made between the Google+ Page and the STEP website in order to provide more effective search results for those looking for topics relevant to the STEP objectives.

It is envisioned that initially YouTube videos will provide the main content for the Google+ page, but this will be extended to additional updates. Automated posting to Google+ from the STEP Twitter account will be

investigated as this would provide a simple mechanism for project partners to contribute or have their contributions recognised on this page.

The link to the STEP Google+ page is: <https://plus.google.com/u/0/101276779269050214597/posts>

4.7 Audiovisual material – YouTube channel

The creation of audiovisual material for the promotion of the STEP project is of crucial importance as such tools are more attractive to young people, even to those who are not so active in other social media. For the STEP project, a YouTube channel will be created with the name “STEP Horizon2020” and will be used for sharing audiovisual material relevant to the project. The audiovisual material will be updated throughout the duration of the project and will include:

- Promotional video with general project information addressed especially to young people
- Promotional video presenting the STEP platform and its advantages
- Simplified step-by-step instructions on how to use the STEP platform
- Simplified step-by-step instructions on how to download and use the STEP mobile application
- Videos from STEP activities, events, meetings, presentations in conferences etc.

Project partners are encouraged to promote the STEP audiovisual material through their websites, their YouTube channels (if available) and other online dissemination tools.

Video uploads will be managed by the WP7 leader.

4.8 Newsletters

Short, regular newsletters will be a key dissemination tool to inform relevant target audiences about the progress of the STEP project. Thus, they will be produced and circulated appropriately every six months and they will consist of brief articles and updates of the STEP project. The STEP newsletters will be circulated in electronic form to the STEP mailing lists and will be available via the project website. Paper copies may be also printed if needed for distribution to stakeholders, community members or attendees of targeted events.

The newsletters will serve as a tool to communicate key updates of the project and as a channel for relevant stakeholders to be kept informed and engaged. Newsletters’ content will be based upon reports filed by partners on events to which the project is presented; key updates on the development of the platform; presentations, workshops and demonstrations; reports, publications and media interest. Partners will be contacted by the WP7 leader for these contributions and/or for their approval of content. The newsletters template, presented in ANNEX C – NEWSLETTER TEMPLATE, follows the STEP project graphical identity and clearly identifies the project as being part of an EU-funded programme.

Some of the topics that will be addressed by the STEP newsletters are:

- Presentation of the project (1st issue)
- Announcements of the project’s progress in brief articles
- News from the pilot cases
- Dates, details, comments regarding project related conferences, meetings, events or publications.

In order to engage as many stakeholders as possible, the STEP partners are encouraged to distribute the newsletters to their contacts who may be interested in the project. Apart from this, interested parties can subscribe to the newsletter on the project’s website.

4.9 Factsheet

This short document will describe in a concise way the project's outline, its goals, key issues, technical approach and expected achievements and impact. In addition, it will contain organisational information of the STEP partners such as contact details and information on the European Commission funding. The factsheet will be a single sheet printed in an A4 size paper, and will be disseminated in formal events (e.g. workshops, conferences, etc.) in order to inform all relevant stakeholders about the key points of the STEP project.

The factsheet will be also available in an online version through the STEP website.

4.10 Press releases

Press releases will be issued whenever important project milestones are executed. They will include important information such as the purpose of the project, milestones reached and results achieved so far, and partners involved. They will target the local or national press of the partners and will describe the goals of the project in a simple, jargon free language, while they will highlight the benefits for a specific region/country if needed.

The project press releases will be launched by the WP7 leader which will inform DRAXIS prior to the release, while any partner that wants to launch a press release is encouraged to contact with the WP7 leader.

4.11 Brochure, leaflet, and poster

The STEP brochure will promote the STEP platform and will serve as a supporting promotion material for the pilot sites. The brochure will be especially designed to raise awareness about the STEP platform pointing out the benefits that users and society will have through the use of the platform. The brochure will contain details about the STEP project, focusing on the project pilots.

The STEP leaflet is already available in a double sided three-folded A4 paper providing an overview of the project in an attractive layout. The leaflet prepared by the WP7 leader is in English and is presented in ANNEX D – STEP LEAFLET. However, the pilot partners are strongly encouraged to translate the leaflet in their language (Italian, Spanish, Catalan, Greek, Turkish) and distribute it to the pilot sites in order to maximise engagement. The leaflet will be circulated by email or printed and distributed at events.

The STEP poster will be designed in order to be used in workshops, conferences and other events organised by the STEP consortium for a short presentation of the project. It is complementary to the leaflet, since the latter provides more detailed information about the project. The main purpose of the poster will be to catch the audience's attention and to engage users as well as potential customers. Among others, the STEP poster will include the following main items:

- STEP Logo – Slogan – Key Words
- EU emblem and statement of the EC funding
- Links for the STEP platform and the project website and STEP QR code
- Eye catchy images to attract attention.

4.12 *Project communication kit*

A project “communication kit” including a) the STEP leaflet in English, b) the STEP poster, and c) an overview STEP presentation will be designed. This will aid the STEP dissemination activities and ensure a consistent communication of the project concept, objectives and results. The STEP communication kit will be distributed at project workshops and conferences in which project partners will participate (see Chapter 5.6 Participation in targeted events).

During the lifetime of the project, the STEP presentation will be constantly updated (at least twice). The first version will disseminate the objectives, the concept and vision of STEP. When project results become available, they will be included in a subsequent version.

4.13 *Other dissemination material*

In order to ensure that there is a vibrant and memorable presence for STEP at non-project events it is anticipated that physical promotional material will be produced. This will include flyers, USB sticks/ cards, pencils, t-shirts, and other dissemination material displaying the STEP logo. The promotional material produced will be clearly identified with the EU emblem. Pilot partners are committed to use this promotional material in order to support user engagement activities. This material will be distributed at city halls of the pilot municipalities, and displayed on blackboards in public buildings, universities, transport information centres, relevant events, etc.

5 *Dissemination activities*

The following sections outline the dissemination activities envisioned to be carried out in the scope of the STEP project.

5.1 *Network of Interest*

The establishment and management of a Network of Interest will be an ongoing activity during the entire life of the project, as well as after the end of the project. The aim of the establishment of a Network of Interest is to act as a main dissemination pole for the engagement of the STEP target groups.

This Network of Interest will encompass individuals of all relevant roles. Specifically our efforts will focus on identifying and engaging representatives of European and national youth associations and environmental NGOs, representatives of EU projects with objectives similar to the ones of STEP, experts in the field of environmental protection, Universities and Research Centres active in the fields of environment and youth participation, and experts with high-level knowledge and experience in policy making and environmental issues. An initial contact list containing contact information of potential members of the STEP Network of Interest has been prepared.

These individuals are expected to be interested in the results of STEP and, therefore, the STEP consortium will try to keep them up to date about the project progress and will encourage them to participate in technical/scientific discussions generated by the consortium.

The STEP Network of Interest will provide the necessary knowledge to the project partners in order to disseminate the project objectives on local, regional, national and European level. The detailed activities that

will be executed to establish the initial contact list and recruitment for the Network of Interest will be elaborated in deliverable D7.4 (M12).

5.2 Mass media communication

The scope of the mass media communication activities will be to inform the general public about the STEP project. These activities will target a wide variety of news agencies and mass media with general or specialised interests. The STEP consortium intends to disseminate the STEP project through TV and radio channels, web media, and newspapers and magazines - either printed or electronic ones. Such a channel is the official web portal of the European Commission (<http://ec.europa.eu/research/index.cfm>) that reaches a wide audience and provides information on EU-funded research. Through this website information on and links to the STEP project will be accessible to the general public, the research community, policy-makers and the media. EurActiv (<http://www.euractiv.com/>) is another portal to which posts relevant to the STEP project will be uploaded. EurActiv is an independent and multilingual EU policy portal that targets mainly the community of EU actors: EU institutions, industry and unions, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), media, countries, regions and cities.

Only selected information will be published in mass media, and the information will be presented in a clear and accessible format for people of all educational levels.

Mass media will be fed through the following dissemination tools:

- press releases
- audiovisual material that will be uploaded at Youtube channel
- project results and newsfeed that will be available at the project's website
- audiovisual or printed material with information about the STEP meetings
- project's presentations and partners' interviews that could be performed during the organisation of targeted events or participation in non-project events.

In order to avoid discrepancies among the information that will be communicated in mass media from the project partners, the WP7 leader is going to prepare an indicative interview template. The STEP partners are encouraged to disseminate the STEP project through mass media on a regular basis. However, the official contact with the mass media will be held by the WP7 leader through the official email account of the STEP project.

An indicative list of mass media active in the countries of the project partners is presented in ANNEX E – MASS MEDIA & NEWS AGENCIES.

5.3 Press releases

Press releases will be prepared in English. However, all partners are encouraged to translate them in their native language. The STEP target is 30 entries at European, national, regional and local press (printed or online) describing the goals of the project in a simple, jargon-free language. Whenever possible, press releases will highlight the benefits for the municipality/region/country and the importance of the local partner being part of an EU consortium. All press releases will be archived and will be available to the public through the project website.

The STEP press releases will be disseminated to the EC Research & Innovation website, which is heavily involved in communicating the results of EU-funded research to the media and the general public

(<http://ec.europa.eu/research/index.cfm?lg=en>). The STEP press releases may, also, be submitted in the Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS) Wire (http://cordis.europa.eu/news/home_en.html), which offers to journalists the ability to download press releases relevant to EU-funded research.

AlphaGalileo (<http://www.alphagalileo.org/>) is another resource for European research news which the STEP consortium will contact so that it publishes STEP press releases. The leader of WP7 will register at the website as a contributor in order to have the right to post press releases, event information, access the address book and view the complete reference library.

Other channels through which the STEP press releases can be disseminated are the press office of the European Environment Agency (<http://www.eea.europa.eu/media#presscontact>), and the Digital Agenda for Europe (<http://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en>).

The STEP partners are, also, encouraged to issue press releases at European Commission's representation offices of their countries (http://ec.europa.eu/contact/local_offices_en.htm). Moreover, an indicative list of national and local media for potential distribution of STEP press releases is presented in ANNEX E – MASS MEDIA & NEWS AGENCIES.

It is worth mentioning that the first press release was issued in the first month of the project targeting the mass media. This press release was in English and partners' native language, and aimed to inform the general public about the kick-off meeting of the project on the 2nd and 3rd of June 2015 and the initiation of the project implementation.

5.4 Publications

It is expected that the STEP project will result in a number of publications in scientific, peer-reviewed journals. Project partners are encouraged to collaborate with each other and jointly prepare publications relevant to the STEP project. Scientific journals that provide open access (OA) to all their publications will be preferred, as it is required by the European Commission.

The target audience will be the scientific community in the fields of ICT, e-government, e-participation, youth participation, policy making, and environment. A list of relevant scientific journals is presented in ANNEX F – RELEVANT JOURNALS.

5.5 Posts in non-project channels

Posts about news and results of the STEP project will be uploaded to non-project channels such as blogs, LinkedIn and Facebook groups, and EU websites.

Furthermore, the WP7 leader will post STEP news in various LinkedIn groups relevant to e-participation, e-governance, environmental policy making, sustainability, and youth participation. Indicatively, the following LinkedIn groups will be reached:

- Future of Government
- edemocracy professionals group
- Environmental Impact Assessment
- Environmental Health and Safety Professionals
- e-government/e-citizen
- Decision Makers Group
- Policy Making 2.0
- Sustainability Professionals
- Environmental social science.

5.6 Participation in targeted events

A common way to achieve an effective dissemination is the participation of the STEP partners in targeted events where STEP will be presented. The events may include workshops relevant to the project objectives, road shows, interactive simulation events, fair hunts/ walkrounds, clean up and/ or restore activities, food festivals, thematic parades, and other creative events.

Relevant reports and photos from the events will be communicated via the STEP website, social media and mass media. During the events, dissemination material, such as brochures and leaflets, will be distributed to the participants. The participation in such events will be led by the respective partner in each country. However, the general coordination will be performed by the WP7 leader. All partners are encouraged to inform the WP7 leader about relevant European, national and local events where STEP may be presented.

An indicative list of targeted events relevant to the STEP objectives is presented in ANNEX G – TARGETED EVENTS.

5.6.1 Scientific conferences

Scientific conferences are key venues to present new scientific knowledge and methodologies emerging from the STEP project. **Partners' representatives will participate in major conferences of relevant fields presenting the STEP project and its objectives. Indicatively:**

- 14th IFIP Electronic Government (EGOV) and 7th Electronic Participation (ePart) Conference 2015, August 30 - September 3, 2015, Thessaloniki, Greece
- e-Democracy 2015 : 6th International Conference on e-Democracy - Citizen rights in the world of the new computing paradigms, December 10-11, 2015, Athens, Greece
- ICDGS 2016 - International Conference on e-Democracy, e-Government and e-Society, January 2016, Paris
- ICBG 2016 - 18th International Conference on e-Business and e-Government, January 12 - 13, 2016, Zurich, Switzerland
- ICEG 2016 - 18th International Conference on e-Government, March 17 - 18, 2016 in London, United Kingdom
- CeDEM16 - International Conference for E-Democracy and Open Government, May 2016, Austria
- ECEG 2016 - 16th European Conference on e-Government, June 2016, Ljubljana, Slovenia
- dg.o 2016 - 17th Annual International Conference on Digital Government Research, Shanghai, China - <https://dgsociety.org/conference/about#2016>

5.6.2 Workshops, road shows, TEDx events

The STEP partners will participate in key workshops on the fields of e-government, e-participation and ICT solutions throughout the duration of the STEP project in order to increase the project's visibility and build the STEP contact list and the Network of Interest.

Road shows and TEDx events will be also useful means to disseminate the STEP project in different target audiences than those attended workshops. Road shows will be held in STEP pilot countries in order to generate excitement and interest in the STEP project, engage youth and find potential customers. Moreover, the consortium aims to participate in TEDx and TEDxYouth events across Europe in order to present the STEP project from a different viewpoint and attract young people to participate. All partners are encouraged to inform the WP7 leader about such events to be held in their region.

Within the duration of the project, the STEP partners aim to participate in 12 workshops and roadshows, in which it is expected that at least 500 young participants will take part.

5.6.3 Open events

Interactive simulation events: This type of activity covers all specialised activities to be organised on local level, tailor-made for the specific conditions, in order to engage young people in interaction within a specific concept, concerning the environment. The aim of these activities is, on the one hand, to reach out for the local youth, with the participation of local youth organisations, clubs and NGOs, in order to encourage them to be engaged in participatory activities (team building activities). On the other hand, the general objective is through the participation of the targeted audience to produce and exploit specific outcomes, in order to raise awareness of the stakeholders concerned in environmental policy issues, regarding youth participation (local authorities, social and business stakeholders, etc.). The concept of the events is to be decided according to the respective background situation and the specifications of the targeted audiences, ranging, indicatively, from simulation events (e.g. model councils), to participatory gamification events (e.g. quizzes, mazes, creative activities). The concept could include distributed/ shared ICT and social media applications (mobile/ Facebook apps) or other types of technologies that will engage young people in interaction within the concept, resulting to a specific output (e.g. video, thread/ log, etc.) that will attract their attention and increase the project dissemination.

Fair Hunts/ Walkrounds: The STEP partners will disseminate the project through interactive fair hunts and walkrounds. During fair hunts or walkrounds participants submit a question(s) for the hunt, the answer to which can be found in their exhibit. A list of questions will be handed out along with hints and tips of where the answer can be found. This list of questions becomes the hunt. Local media (TV and radio stations) will be involved by passing out the forms, collecting and "grading" them and giving out prizes. These activities will increase the environmental education of the participants, and offer a great publicity vehicle for the STEP project.

Clean up and/ or restore activities: The STEP partners will participate in the organisation of clean-up and restore activities in collaboration with youth organisations, cultural associations and local clubs mainly in the pilot sites. Clean-up activities may be conducted in rivers, lakes, streams, beaches, trails, communities or graffiti. Participants will have the chance to be informed about the STEP project, while dissemination material will be distributed to the volunteers.

Food Festivals: Food is a fun feature at any event and always draws a bigger crowd than for non-food events. The environmental consequences of food related issues are far-reaching and multi-sectoral. The event could

provide visibility to a local point of view regarding environmental and sustainability issues, with the engagement of local farmers of locally-grown, organic produce. Food festivals with representatives from the natural and organic foods network entice people into learning about the environmental and health impacts of our food choices. Local-food restaurants, nutrition groups and organic food suppliers can also be involved, using the opportunity to raise awareness and educate the community about the global and individual effects of food-related personal habits and the industries connected with those choices.

Thematic parades: Thematic parades encourage creative participation and raise awareness on environmental issues.

Creative events: Creative and artistic concepts will be developed, aiming to encourage young people to participate and express themselves, while participating in project's activities. Simple concepts relevant to the STEP objectives will be developed in wiki-form (such as wiki-theatre plays), enabling participants to adapt and reform the concept according to their preferences, under specific provisions.

Other open events: The STEP consortium may participate in other open events, such as mazes, RPGs, community gardens etc. in order to increase the popularity of the project.

The STEP consortium intends to participate in 2-3 open events in each pilot area, with either educational or motivational character, co-organised in collaboration with local stakeholders (local authorities, NGOs, etc.), with at least 1.200 participants.

5.7 *Organisation of project events*

As the project matures and further results become available, the consortium will organise dissemination events in order to increase youth awareness on the STEP platform and engage further external stakeholders, such as public organisations, NGOs, strategic decision makers, policy makers, think tanks, scholars, public and private administrations etc.

Among these events, one project workshop in each pilot area will be designed, organised and implemented. These workshops will be set up in order to provide an overview of the project objectives and activities, present and discuss the results of the project, and share experiences and lessons learned to stakeholders and scientific community. The workshops will be organised by the leader of WP7 and particular attention will be paid to the participation of the members of the STEP Network of Interest.

In addition to the main project workshops, dedicated workshops for those who are not familiar with the use of digital tools will be conducted in each pilot, aiming to ensure that the STEP procedures will not result in discriminatory practices or unfair treatment. In the same framework, info kiosks will be placed in popular streets for those with no internet access and special dissemination material will be designed and distributed. Organisers of these workshops and responsible for the info kiosks will be the pilot partners.

5.8 *Informal person-to-person meetings*

Although organising one-to-one meetings with interested individuals can be a time consuming task, it will be very useful to target key people who may be interested to use and exploit the STEP platform. Such key people are Mayors and other representatives of European Municipalities, employees of public authorities, policy makers, representatives of NGOs or youth organisations, and individuals with in-depth knowledge in decision making procedures for youth and environment. The target of the informal person-to-person meetings will be twofold, aiming to gain knowledge from key people about the local environmental problems

and, on the other hand, to inform them about the benefits of the STEP platform. The informal person-to-person meetings will be conducted from all the partners throughout the duration of the project, while reports of these meetings will be prepared and disseminated to all project partners.

5.9 Online/ mobile games & applications

Adventure and puzzle-solving flash games and online social applications are going to be created, enriched with educational and targeted content concerning environmental issues, even on local level, providing essential links from and to the STEP platform.

5.10 Collaboration with similar projects/ initiatives

The STEP consortium will identify and reach similar projects and initiatives with the aim of collaboration. Through these collaborations, stakeholders will exchange views and experiences upon topics of common interest, exploit potential synergies, maximise the potential impact for all actors, and guarantee the long-term sustainability of the project. EU-funded or international research projects and initiatives in STEP's research domains will be communicated and invited to participate in project events, while project dissemination material will be distributed to them.

STEP may build synergies with the following EU-funded projects which have relevant objectives with the ones of STEP:

- EUth: Tools and Tips for Digital and Mobile Youth Participation in and across Europe
- PARTISPACE: Spaces and Styles of Participation. Formal, non-formal and informal possibilities of young people's participation in European cities
- CATCH-EyoU: Constructing AcTive CitizensHip with European Youth: Policies, Practices, Challenges and Solutions
- MYPLACE: Memory, youth, political legacy and civic engagement
- SocIEtY: Social innovation – Empowering the young for the common good
- OURSPACE: Online eparticipation platform
- PIDOP: Processes Influencing Democratic Ownership and Participation
- MYUNIVERSITY: Decision making for a united higher education

The STEP partners may, also, collaborate with EU-funded projects of various other topics:

Youth and the World

- POWER2YOUTH: Freedom, dignity and justice: A comprehensive approach to the understanding of youth exclusion and the prospects for youth inclusion and overall change in the South and East Mediterranean
- SAHWA: Empowering the young generation: towards a new social contract in South and East Mediterranean countries

Education and Training

D7.1: 1st Dissemination Plan

- CARE: Curriculum and Quality Analysis and Impact Review of European Early Childhood Education and CARE
- EDUMIGROM: Ethnic differences in Education and the Diverging Prospects for Urban Youth in an Enlarged Europe
- GOETE: Governance of Educational Trajectories in Europe. Access, coping and relevance of education for young people in European knowledge societies in comparative perspective
- Includ-ED: Strategies for Inclusion and Social Cohesion in Europe from Education
- LLLight in Europe: LifeLong Learning|Innovation|Growth & HumanCapital|Tracks in Europe
- RESL.eu: Reducing early school leaving in the EU
- SociEtY: Social innovation - Empowering the young (SociEtY) for the common good
- WorkAble: Making Capabilities Work

Employment and Entrepreneurship

- CUPESSE: Cultural Pathways to Economic Self-sufficiency and Entrepreneurship: Family Values and Youth Unemployment in Europe
- EFESEIIS: Enabling the Flourishing and Evolution of Social Entrepreneurship for Innovative and Inclusive Societies
- INSPIRES: Innovative social and employment policies for inclusive and resilient labour markets in Europe
- MOVE: Mapping mobility – Pathways , institutions and structural effects of youth mobility in EU
- NEGOTIATE: Negotiating early job - Insecurity and labour market exclusion in Europe
- NEUJOBS: Creating and Adapting Jobs in the Context of a Socio- Ecological Transition
- SEFORIS: Social Enterprise as Force for More Inclusive and Innovative Societies
- STYLE: Strategic Transitions for Youth Labour in Europe
- YMOBILITY: Youth mobility: Maximising opportunities for individuals, labour markets and regions in EU

Social Inclusion

- CITISPYCE: Combating inequalities through innovative social practices of, and for, young people in cities across Europe
- COPE: Combating Poverty in Europe: Re-organising Active Inclusion through Participatory and Integrated Modes of Multilevel Governance
- CSEYHP: Combating Social Exclusion among Young Homeless Populations
- DISCIT: Making Persons with Disabilities Full Citizens: New Knowledge for an Inclusive and Sustainable European social Model
- EUMARGINS: On the Margins of the European Community
- EXCEPT: Social exclusion of youth in EU: Cumulative disadvantage, coping strategies, effective policies and transfer
- IMPROVE: Poverty Reduction in Europe: Social Policy and Innovation
- YiPPEE: Young People in Public Care: Pathways to Education in Europe
- YOUNEX: Youth, unemployment, and exclusion in Europe: A multidimensional approach to understanding the conditions and prospects for social and political integration of young unemployed

Health and Well-being

- FamiliesAndSocieties: Changing Families and Sustainable Societies: Policy Contexts and Diversity over the Life Course and across Generations
- MYWeb: Measuring Youth Well-Being

Volunteering

- ITSSOIN: Social Innovation and civic engagement
- THIRD SECTOR IMPACT: The contribution of the third sector to Europe's socio-economic development

Cross-cutting

- SI-DRIVE: Social Innovation: Driving Force of Social Change
- SIMPACT: Boosting the Impact of Social Innovation in Europe through Economic Underpinnings

6 Internal dissemination

This Chapter aims to define the internal communication guidelines that will ensure:

- That all partners have access to the same information at the same time
- That partners are aware of the development status of the STEP platform
- That information is equally fast transmitted to all partners
- That the rules of behaviour are obeyed
- That consistent formats and communication procedures are used
- That the transmitted information minimises overload, is fast accessible and reduced to the essential.

6.1 Document sharing

All the prepared templates of the dissemination material, as well as the final version of all STEP deliverables and any other document that should be circulated among partners will be shared among partners. Currently, Dropbox is temporarily used, but the final means of sharing will be agreed within the following month.

6.2 E-mail communication

As described in Chapter 4.5 E-mail account and mailing lists, a mailing list for the internal communication between the project partners has already been created. This Chapter aims defines the internal communication guidelines through the STEP mailing list as follows:

- For contacting all partners at once, a mailing list has been created
- The mailing list will be maintained and updated if needed by the coordinator. All changes of the mailing list must be sent to the coordinator who will adapt the list as soon as possible.
- To ensure high and continuous coverage when distributing information it is highly recommended that partners use this mailing list
- The e-mail subject should be clearly marked; ideally, all e-mails concerning STEP shall start with “STEP” in the subject, followed by the topic
- Partners should refrain from sending large files via e-mail but rather use the documenting sharing means that will be agreed in order to upload the file and send out only a text e-mail to the target group with the notification about the new content
- All partners have to be aware of computer viruses.

7 Strengths and responsibilities of the project partners

The STEP consortium consists of partners with significant links with stakeholders that have potential interest to the project and with experience in disseminating similar activities.

Indicatively:

- YEE is a European network of youth environmental organisations from 26 countries. The YEE network aims to encourage youth to be involved in environmental protection. Among others it organises and encourages activities that increase the knowledge, understanding and appreciation of nature and the awareness of environmental problems among young people in Europe. A significant part of YEE’s role in the STEP project is to disseminate the project objectives to its members and motivate them to participate.
- The five pilot partners-public authorities (ROC, HATAY, CSB, MDV, VALD) have the potential to spread the STEP information in their area and engage relevant stakeholders (youth, policy makers, general public, etc.).
- DRAXIS cooperates with more than 40 public bodies in the Greek region and has the potential to engage them in the STEP project. Among others, DRAXIS has implemented a pilot of an EU project (the “eEnviPer” project) in the region of Crete in which citizens participated and were given consultation in issues relevant to environmental permits.

All project partners are in a strong position to develop an effective dissemination strategy, building on key existing channels. These channels and links will provide direct access to the target groups and will act as core channels that will support the project’s sustainability and its effective exit strategy.

Regarding the responsibilities of each project partner for the dissemination of STEP, they are summarised in the following table.

Partner	Role
DRAXIS	Oversee and evaluate the dissemination activities Prepare the project logo Develop the project website

	<p>Produce all printed material</p> <p>Organise the project workshops</p> <p>Organise project events</p> <p>Establish and manage the Network of Interest</p>
YEE	Mobilise its members (youth and environmental organisations) to participate in the project events
ROC, HATAY, CSB, MDV, VALD	<p>Mobilise their members (policy makers and relevant stakeholders) to participate</p> <p>Organise project events in their area</p>
All partners	<p>Disseminate the results to the public, and ensure the participation of youth/ general public</p> <p>Participate and present the project in events organised by third parties</p> <p>Feed information to website and social media</p> <p>Publish articles</p> <p>Translate and develop informational material</p> <p>Suggest contacts for the project mailing list and the Network of Interest</p> <p>Provide performance data to the WP7 leader</p>

8 Monitoring, Reporting & Evaluation

To ensure accurate monitoring and reporting of dissemination activities, STEP deliverables include a number of reports linked to dissemination activities. The WP7 leader will be responsible for drafting the content of these reports, under the guidance of DRAXIS. The following sections outline the STEP reporting schedule, as well as the requirements for individual partners to provide information on their own dissemination activities.

The reporting schedule for the formal STEP dissemination deliverables is as follows:

- Nov 2015 Dissemination pack (D7.2)
- May 2016 Report: Dissemination activities (D7.3)
- Report: Network of Interest (D7.4)
- Report: Dissemination Plan (Update) (D7.7)
- April 2017 Report: Network of Interest (Update) (D7.6)
- May 2017 Report: Dissemination activities (Update) (D7.5)
- Nov 2017 Report: Dissemination activities (Update) (D7.8)
- Report: Network of Interest (Update) (D7.9)

This involves four main types of reports and updates:

- The Dissemination Plan (this document) and update
- The Dissemination pack
- Annual Reports on the Network of Interest
- Annual Reports on Dissemination activities

As mentioned above, the leader of WP7 will be in charge of the overall monitoring of all dissemination activities and will report to the project coordinator in case of any problem. However, each partner will be in charge of locally monitoring its own dissemination activity and reporting the progress and pitfalls to the WP7 leader. All partners are responsible for liaising with national and local media for dissemination purposes, and for ensuring that they engage enough stakeholders to properly enlarge the community. Each partner has already nominated a dissemination contact point who will send the following to the WP7 leader on a regular basis (i.e. whenever there are activities to report on, at latest a week after the activity):

1. A description of all dissemination publications published or posted by project partner or other organisations, using the template for monitoring dissemination activities in Annex H1 Template for Reporting Dissemination Publications
2. A description of all dissemination events held using the template for dissemination events in Annex H2 Template for Reporting Dissemination Events.

To facilitate reporting, these templates have been designed to be as simple and easy to fill in as possible. The WP7 leader stresses the importance of receiving this information to allow the accurate monitoring and adjustment of dissemination activities as necessary. Moreover, project partners are asked to send to the WP7 leader any photocopy, print-out, photo, link, screenshot, etc. relevant to the project whenever they find them.

Regarding the evaluation of STEP's dissemination activities, a specific ongoing evaluation procedure will be executed so that the impact of the dissemination strategy can be measured in all the project phases from its very beginning to its end. The main issues that will be evaluated are the quality of the dissemination tools and activities, and the impact of the dissemination activities on the target groups defined by the project, emphasising on the impact of the project on young women and special social groups such as youth with physical disabilities, young living in mountainous and disadvantaged areas etc.

As described in Chapter 9 Dissemination impact indicators, the achievement of the objectives of the STEP dissemination strategy will be evaluated by assessing the dissemination impact indicators in comparison with the predefined target values. Regular updates of the project achievements will be communicated, including results (presentations, press releases, participation in events, etc.) which will be highlighted on the STEP website, social media groups/accounts, etc.

For each of the dissemination activities, one or more measurement or feedback mechanisms will be used to measure the effectiveness of the dissemination. Indicatively:

- **Website:** Setup Google Analytics and measure the number of visitor/ traffic to the website/ amount of time spent on the site
- **Facebook:** Number of “likes”
- **LinkedIn, Twitter, Google+, YouTube:** Number of group memberships
- **Project events:** Number of STEP events organised by the consortium; number of participants
- **Non-project events:** Number of non-project events in which STEP is presented; number of participants
- **Newsletter:** Number of newsletters promoted; number of subscribed people
- **Project printed material:** Distribution rate versus website traffic
- **Publications:** Number of publications and audience per publication; traffic rate on the website
- **Press releases/ articles:** Coverage (number of media), frequency (positive or negative media evaluation), level of involvement of news agencies in dissemination
- **Network of Interest:** Number of stakeholders registered
- **Other initiatives:** Level of collaboration with other similar initiatives; number of joint events.

9 Dissemination impact indicators

In order to quantify and evaluate the dissemination actions, STEP sets specific measurable goals with respect to the aforementioned planned activities. Specifically the following indicators are set as minimum expected dissemination targets.

Indicator	Target Value	Source/ methodology
Number of visits to the project website	45,000	Google analytics
Number of followers in the social media accounts that will be opened	12,000	Accounts' data
Number of women followers in the social media accounts that will be opened	6,000	Accounts' data
Number of open events (clean-up/ restore events, thematic parades, food festival etc.)	6	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of participants in the open events (clean-up/ restore events, thematic parades, food festival etc.)	1,200	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of young participants in the open events (clean-up/ restore events, thematic parades, food festival etc.)	800	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of female participants in the open events (clean-up/ restore events, thematic parades, food festival etc.)	600	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of targeted events (workshops, roadshows)	12	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of young participants in the targeted events (workshops, roadshows)	500	Participants' lists
Number of female participants in the targeted events	300	Participants' lists

(workshops, roadshows)		
Number of non-project events where STEP project will be presented	6	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of entries (articles/ press releases) in local, regional and national press (printed and online)	30	Copies of the entries
Number of e-newsletters promoted	10	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of newsletters recipients	6,000	Mailing list record
Number of distributed printed material	4,000	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of viewers of project related audiovisual material	2,000	Number of views through YouTube
Number of stakeholders registered in the STEP network of interest	1,000	List of stakeholders
Number of scientific papers published	2	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project

10 Timeplan for the first year of the project

The dissemination activities and the relevant action plan that will be executed within the first year of the STEP project are presented in the following Table.

Activity	Month											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
STEP website												
-Finalise website's initial content												
-Upload STEP website		X	X	X	X							
-Create links to the project website through the project partners' webpages												
STEP mailing lists												
-Create the STEP internal mailing list	X					X						
-Create the STEP external mailing list for dissemination material distribution												
Deliverables												
-Prepare and submit deliverables D7.1, D7.2, D7.3, D7.4, and D7.7	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Social media - Create LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, Google+, and YouTube groups/accounts -Invite members/friends/followers for STEP social media groups/accounts		X	X										
Brochure, leaflet, factsheet -Prepare content for project brochure, leaflet and factsheet -Distribute leaflet to project partners -Distribute brochure, leaflet and factsheet in relevant events, similar initiatives, and interested stakeholders							X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Newsletter -Prepare and distribute STEP newsletters						X							X
Poster -Prepare and print the project's general poster					X								
Publications/ Articles -Distribute scientific/ technical articles about the project in journals -Articles about the project in various sectoral editions (magazines, newsletters of associations, etc.)													X
Press releases -Identification of European and national media with high visibility -Identification of important project milestones and events for which press releases should be prepared -Preparation of content and dissemination of press releases	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Audiovisual material -Preparation of STEP audiovisual material										X	X	X	
Participation in relevant events -Identification of international events, seminars and conferences and information of other partners -Identification of events, seminars and			X										X

conferences at national level												
-Poster/ presentations in international events												
-Presentations in similar initiatives events												
Project events												
-Discussion/ agreement on the events' context			X							X		
-Agreement of project events to be organised in 2016												
Collaboration with similar projects/ initiatives												
-Identification of similar projects/initiatives			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
-Communication with similar projects/initiatives												

11 Conclusions

Through the implementation of this Dissemination Plan, STEP will encourage young people and policy makers across Europe to invest in the STEP platform. Its impact depends on the successful configuration of the existing software and the implementation of the pilot projects. As the project evolves, the Dissemination Plan will be adjusted to match the results and impacts of the project. An updated Dissemination Plan will be published in May 2016.

ANNEX A-PROJECT PARTNERS

A.1 DRAXIS ENVIRONMENTAL S.A. (DRAXIS)

DRAXIS was founded in 2000 in Thessaloniki, Greece, to focus on providing consulting, solution development, implementation and management of environmental technologies. DRAXIS helps local authorities or private organisations in the improvement of natural resource usage and integration of environmental management issues into the decision-making process. Through the combined use of Geographic Information System technologies, environmental know-how and environmental remote sensing and database software products, DRAXIS' clients can achieve substantial improvements in their environmental performance. DRAXIS provides excellent services, high environmental performance and information security through its management system implemented in accordance with ISO 9001:2008 (Quality Management), ISO 14001:2004 (Environmental Management) and ISO 27001:2005 (Information Security Management).

A.2 CENTRE FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY HELLAS (CERTH)

The Information Technologies Institute was founded in 1998 as a non-profit organisation with its head office located in Thessaloniki, Greece. Since 2000 it has been a founding member of the Centre of Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH). The CERTH research involved in SocialSensor focuses on the following R&D areas: semantic multimedia analysis, indexing and retrieval, large-scale and social media analysis, knowledge structures, languages and reasoning for content analysis, personalization and knowledge discovery for Semantic Web applications. The team has participated in more than 50 EC IST and 85 National projects and subcontracts. Over the last eight years, the CERTH team has authored over 200 publications in journals, 65 books and book chapters and over 500 presentations to international conferences.

A.3 LINGUATEC GMBH (LINGUATEC) GMBH

Linguattec is an SME company, founded 1992 in Munich, Germany. With a dedicated team of computational linguists, language experts and computer scientist, Linguattec develops innovative language technology solutions which enable people throughout the world to increase their productivity and communication. Linguattec focuses on the following areas: 1) Machine Translation: Linguattec solution "Personal Translator" is the leading MT system in Germany, with a hybrid architecture using statistical and corpus-based extensions to a rule-based system backbone; 2) Speech Recognition: Linguattec offers the "Voice Pro" product line (general dictation, special systems for legal and medical domain). This product has scored best in the evaluation of Stiftung Warentest (German consumer magazine). 3) Speech Synthesis: Linguattec markets a product line "VoiceReader", for more than 25 languages, in applications from iPhone apps to server-based installations for corporate customers. 4) Natural Language Tools: Dictionaries, phrase books, text mining, morphological analysers and aligners, available for PVs and mobile devices (Linguadict). Linguattec runs a free dictionary portal under www.linguadict.de. The European Commission has awarded Linguattec with the European Information Technology Prize in 1996, 1998 and 2004 for its leading-edge language technology solutions, Linguattec being the first company ever to have won this prestigious prize three times.

A.4 THE UNIVERSITY COURT OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ABERTAY DUNDEE (ABERTAY)

Abertay is a modern University based in Dundee, Scotland (UK). Abertay is a recognised centre of expertise in digital and interactive media and their applications to addressing societal challenges. Abertay has

international recognition for activities in teaching and Knowledge Exchange on interactive media (UK Centre for Excellence in Games Development; UK Prototype Fund for games development,). Abertay's strategy is to integrate the disciplines of computer arts, interactive computer graphics and psychology to design (arts, psychology), develop (arts, graphics) and evaluate (psychology) computer-based solutions to industry problems. Abertay possess extensive experiences in the areas of digital games, user research and the application of these to answer societal challenges. Key Abertay Departments and personnel involved in the project reflect the University expertise, with participation of the Sociology Department (user research), Digital Games Department (gamification, co-production) and Psychology Department (evaluation, user research).

A.5 INMARK ESTUDIOS Y ESTRATEGIAS SA (INMARK)

INMARK is a business and marketing consulting firm based in Madrid, with relevant background in business intelligence and innovation management. INMARK has a track record of 35 years in business in Europe and Latin America. INMARK has branches in 7 countries, totaling some 200 qualified staff members. INMARK delivers market research fieldwork, analytic and strategic marketing studies for leading financial banking institutions (business and consumer banking and strategic brand positioning), governments (tourism and bus & metro public transportation of Madrid) and ICT industry analysts, covering the different market segments: hardware, software and services in IT and telecommunications (voice and data), digital media, channels of distribution, security, SOA and ICT in vertical markets (bank, insurance, e-Government, e-learning and health). Inmark has a wide experience accrued in participating in more than 40 EU funded RTD and Innovation Projects.

A.6 REGION OF CRETE (ROC)

Region of Crete is a second grade local self-government authority and offers services for the benefit of the citizens. It consists of 6 General Directorates and 36 Directorates that aim at Economic, Social and Cultural Development of the Island. Region of Crete designs, plans and implements policies at the regional level as part of its responsibility in accordance with the principles of sustainable development and social cohesion of the country, taking into account national and European policies. Region of Crete has great experience in implementing National and European projects. Under this scope, several actions of information, promotion and diffusion of knowledge have been carried out, while some of the projects were brought into effect in co-operation with other bodies, even from abroad. Through the Directorate of Environmental and Spatial Planning, and according to the national law for the environmental permits and the protection of the environment, Region of Crete is involved in the relative administrative procedures.

A.7 SAMPAS BILISIM VE ILETISIM SISTEMLERI SANAYI VE TICARET A.S. (SAMPAS)

Founded in February 1981, SAMPAS (Large Enterprise) is the leading Turkish IT company which introduced the Smart City concept to Turkey, providing information management tools and project management services - tailored for the specific needs of the local authorities. Providing service just for the municipal corporations as from its establishment date, SAMPAS offers the end to end solutions concerning informatics for municipalities, which are in need of outsourcing, software, data set and hardware services, successfully. Sampaş has been offering various services to over 400 municipalities in Turkey such as, GIS solutions, urban planning and transformation projects, mobile solutions, intelligent transport solutions, and recently smart water management solutions. Besides, Sampaş has been gaining experience in cloud computing and developing software projects with SOA architecture for several years and using its experience in both

national and international projects (ITEA2, Celtic, ICT-PSP) experiences in architecture definition, service implementation, pilot demonstrators and dissemination for several projects.

A.8 HATAY METROPOLITAN MUNICIPALITY (HATAY)

Hatay is one of the biggest cities in the Mediterranean region of Turkey with its population of 1,503,066 and with its 12 districts. Hatay is a growing city and recently became a Metropolitan Municipality. Hatay's main sources of income are agriculture, trade, tourism and import-export. Although the agriculture, trade and import-export play a big role on the economy of the city, the potential of the industry has improved with the establishment of Iskenderun Iron and Steel Plant. It can be easily said that Hatay Metropolitan Municipality is one of the most innovative and IT oriented municipalities of Turkey with its' several smart city projects. Protection and decontamination of the environment is one of the priority responsibilities of the Hatay Metropolitan Municipality. To do so, Hatay Metropolitan Municipality discusses environment related issues in the City Council established from the representatives of NGO's and citizen groups for the sustainable development of Hatay. Municipality also offers services through the work of its Environmental Protection and Control Department which is responsible for the minimization of the air and noise pollution, makes projects about excavation wastes and environment and licensing issues.

A.9 COMUNE DI SANT'AGATA DEL BIANCO (CSB)

Sant'Agata del Bianco is a small municipality in the province of Reggio Calabria, an administrative division of Calabria region. Sant'Agata is a member of Locride Municipalities Association which represents and safeguards the collective interest of the municipalities of Locride Area at regional and national level, as well as to promote the development and democracy. The municipality promote a policy of environmental protection through projects financed by European funds POR Calabria, the RDP (Rural Development Plan) and the PIAR (Integrated Plans for Rural Areas). The purpose of these projects is to preserve the natural environment with its biodiversity exalting and enhancing local production, recovery craft and the huge cultural heritage. These actions will lead to the creation of a sustainable economy that will enable local residents to be able to combat the phenomenon of depopulation of inland areas and mountainous. Moreover, the Municipality is equipped with a system for the recycling of waste with a collection door to door. At the same time the public lighting system is adequate with an energy-saving system and photovoltaic panels have been installed from 20 kW / h which effectively make the local primary school and the municipal building and public buildings generally autonomous. Together with the Association of Municipalities of Locride areas the Municipality is partner of the European project Philoxeniaplus project in the frame of Med capitalisation program to combat the depopulation of areas internal.

A.10 YEE-YOUTH AND ENVIRONMENT EUROPE (YEE)

Youth and Environment Europe (YEE) is a network of 45 European youth environmental organisations from 26 countries. The aim of YEE is to encourage youth to be involved in environmental protection and to provide a platform where these organisations can work together. YEE gives an opportunity to contact other European organisations, to exchange experiences and ideas and to create common projects. All YEE's activities are organised and carried out by young volunteers under 30. YEE organises and encourages all activities that can increase the knowledge, understanding and appreciation of nature and the awareness of environmental problems among young people in Europe. YEE serves member organisations to exchange information, ideas and experience among them, through publications and European projects, like training courses, youth exchanges, and seminars. YEE focuses on youth participation and non-formal education and organises projects to increase skills of young people and empower them to be active citizens.

A.11 AJUNTAMENT DE MOLLET DEL VALLES (MDV)

Mollet del Vallès is a small city of the metropolitan area of Barcelona. The average population of Mollet is young people, with an average of 38.5 years. At present, a new "plan of youth" is being discussed. The plan consists of the formation, artistic creation, welfare and health, and entrepreneurship. The city council has put into motion a group of actions through electronic and Internet network to facilitate the citizen participation and the governance, and the processing and electronic relation with the economic and social agents of the city and the territory, through platforms of procedures and circuits of negotiations with the industrials. The orientation of the city is done with the Strategic Plan of the City Mollet2025, which has the evaluation, follow-up and impulse of a group of experts of the city. Basically, the three basic points to be developed are: to advance in the civic and the education of the city; to renew and describe the urban and rural spaces in cooperation with the territory; and to promote greater economic activity and health and sustainability. A few weeks ago, a new Registration of Citizenship participation has joined the Registration of entities in order to inform and facilitate the participative action for people interested in being informed about the processes of participation in the topics that they are interested in. Finally, Mollet of the Vallès has a European vocation for its strategic situation in the Mediterranean corridor, as it is twinned with the city of Rivoli (Italy), Ravensburg (Germany), Kranj (Slovenia), and Montelimar (France). This European relation is based in the collaboration and exchange between the youngsters, especially the students of secondary education and traditional entities. These twinned cities are driving the group of the small European cities for the peace.

A.12 KAIROS FUTURE AKTIEBOLAG (KAIROS)

KAIROS is an international research and consulting organization active in the field of foresight, strategy and innovation. KAIROS has for many years been active in several fields. It has worked with local municipalities and regions, as well as youth, environment and other NGOs in research as well as consulting projects. Many of the projects undertaken have been based on participative methods in which many citizens have been engaged. Environmental issues have been a centerpiece in many projects over the years, and several of our researchers and consultants have a strong background in the field. Youth studies and youth related projects are another field of expertise that is at the core of our activities. The latest major study that was undertaken in 2013 was a global survey of youth values across the globe. Finally, the company has developed a smartphone based co-creation platform (Co:tunity) aimed to engage people in participative development work. Co:tunity is a unique multi-functional smartphone application and web based platform for collaborative trendspotting and innovation. With Co:tunity users can easily gather, share and develop trends and ideas, analyse and report in the same digital platform. The core functionality enables Policy Makers to engage a crowd (Citizen Panel) in trend spotting and idea development. People can browse or be invited to public or private challenges and share spotting or suggestions. Analysts can capture and structure these posts into trends or ideas and then define and analyse these together.

A.13 AYUNTAMIENTO DE VALDEMORO (VALD)

Valdemoro City is a municipal district, located in the Southern zone of the autonomous community of Madrid, Spain. Valdemoro has one of the highest growth rates in Madrid Community and one of the largest absolute population growths in Spain. The population of Valdemoro is very young and active; 22% of the population is younger than 15 years old and 7% of the population was older than 65, a percentage that is significantly smaller than the 15% average of Madrid Region. Due to the recent population boom, Valdemoro has had to construct new transportation, educational, sanitation, health, and entertainment facilities. In this regard Valdemoro follows a strategic plan to move towards next digital decade; especially in two areas:

education and youth, and sustainable mobility. Through the education area there is a strong plan for youth to improve personal and citizenship development supporting formation, artistic, entrepreneurship, health and social advancement. The environmental initiative led by Madrid city council of Sustainable Use of Energy and Climate Change Prevention proposes a new energy model for Madrid that the answer to the economic, social, environmental and technological developments that the city is experiencing, and future challenges. Valdemoro will sensitise youth towards use of bicycles and non-motor vehicles, saving of energy and non-renewable resources, efficient use of energy and a low carbon economy, as a means to combat climate change and contribute to a better economic, social and territorial citizenship responsibility and conscience as well as cultural awareness. This will be coupled with the sustainable mobility and urban plans and diffusion strategies of the City. As part of the transparency and digital city objectives, Valdemoro city council has put into motion a group of actions through electronic and Internet network to facilitate citizen participation and governance; including availability of e-platforms for processing and having electronic relation for transactions with the economic and social agents of the city and the territory; e-participation and suggestions for education and sustainable mobility. As part of the international approach, Valdemoro is twinned with other European city councils, for example Godolo City Council in Hungary.

ANNEX B – LOCAL DISSEMINATION STRATEGIES

B.o Local Dissemination Strategy Outline

Within the context of the general Dissemination Strategy of the project, a specialised Dissemination Strategy outline has been developed, in order to provide guidelines for the planning and implementation of each one of the Local Dissemination Strategies in the pilot areas. The Local Dissemination Strategy outline is ensuring, on the one hand, a common approach of the use of the dissemination activities and tools, while, on the other hand, is providing the conditions for the necessary specialisation on each distinct area. For this to be realised, a 4-phase approach is being outlined, aiming to engage all the involved parties on local level in order to implement the Dissemination Strategy, based on the specific needs and conditions of each area.

In order to do so, a preliminary analysis has been elaborated for the identification of the specific requirements and current condition of each area, as well as the stakeholders involved, regarding the dissemination objectives and targeted audiences. The analysis is being coordinated by the WP7 leader using desk-based research and interviews, with the contribution of the partners providing primary data with the use of semi-structured questionnaires.

B.o.1 Local Dissemination Strategy phases

The dissemination strategy is structured in four distinct phases in order to make use of a variety of activities and tools. Using distinct channels through a circular flow of 4 dissemination streams, the dissemination strategy aims to combine global knowledge and expertise with local first-hand experience, in creating local action motivation, in order to raise awareness and enhance participation. This scheme will engage the interested parties into interaction, aiming to:

- Ensure commitment in participation from an interdisciplinary group of experts (“Commitment” stream)

- Spread current knowledge and raise awareness on environmental policy (“Knowledge” stream)
- Engage local stakeholders (local authorities, businesses, youth and environmental NGOs, etc.) into participatory activities, creating action motivation coalitions among each other and with the partners of the STEP project on local level, acting themselves as dissemination poles (“Action motivation” stream)
- Engage young people in participating in participatory events and joining the coalitions, using the tools provided by the STEP project to communicate their message regarding environmental policy, creating a local pressure group (“Experience” stream)
- Create a constant feedback loop returning to the Network of Interest, using the experience from the previous phases and providing dissemination of the results of the activities.

More specifically, the dissemination processes taking place in each phase are described as follows:

1st Phase: Commitment of the Network of Interest

During the first phase, the project partners who are responsible for the implementation of the local dissemination strategy make use of the project’s communication tools and channels to ensure commitment of experts from related fields with high-level of knowledge and experience in policy making and environmental issues. The objective is to form a Network of Interest in order to act as a main dissemination pole to the next phase.

2nd Phase: Knowledge exchange

During the second phase the project, partners together with the Network of Interest provide the necessary knowledge dissemination towards the most interested and active parties on local level. Through a number of interactive information and knowledge exchange events (workshops, TEDx events, etc.) targeted to local stakeholders (local NGOs and youth & environmental organisations, active communities, etc.) as well as local authorities and business bodies and other stakeholders concerned on local level (journalists, local media, etc.), knowledge and experience is being exchanged, with the objective to build synergies in order to co-organise participatory events targeted to young people in the next phase.

3rd Phase: Action motivation

During the third phase a set of participatory events will be organised jointly by the project partners with the interested parties from the 2nd phase. The activities will be especially targeted to enhance participation from young men and women from local level, disseminating the projects objectives towards them, while providing them with the appropriate tools and motivate them to participate actively in the activities of the project, mainly the STEP platform, in order to communicate their own message to the parties concerned (local authorities, policy making bodies, etc.). At the same time, the results of the participatory events will provide useful experience data for experts (Network of Interest) in order to expand and assess the current knowledge and disseminate the project’s outcomes.

4th Phase: Feedback and Dissemination

The fourth phase includes all dissemination streams that will result from the experience gained by the first three phases. All the above concerned parties (project partners, field experts, local stakeholders, young participants, etc.) will make use and exploit the experience from the dissemination activities (information events, participatory events), as means of communicating themselves and creating a positive pressure stream towards the stakeholders concerned with policy making and environmental policy, on local and global level. In this way, the knowledge exchange and participatory action taking place in the first 3 phases will result in the necessary data and experience for:

- project partners to disseminate the project’s outcomes and participatory experience from the targeted audience
- local stakeholders (NGOs, active communities, etc.) to enhance their capacity in dissemination activities
- young men and women in enhancing their participation in decision making on local level.

The project’s outputs from the 4th phase will be publications and mass media entries, newsletters and information and publicity activities (e.g. participation in events, public presentations, etc.) aiming to diffuse the knowledge and experience gained, targeted to all concerned parties on local and global level (academia & experts, policy making stakeholders, local authorities, NGOs, young people, etc.). Furthermore, all the participating parties are expected to act as multipliers of the project’s outcomes, using the tools provided, including the eParticipation platform, in creatively expressing and communicating themselves in the public sphere, creating further dissemination streams towards the targeted audiences.

The abovementioned relationship is illustrated in the following Figure:

Figure 6: Local Dissemination Strategy phases

Within the context of the above, for the implementation of each Local Dissemination Strategy the outlined phases will provide guidance for the specification of the use of the proper activities and tools. Based on this approach, a general description of the local dissemination activities is provided in the next section, covering the respective activities for the objectives of each phase.

The description of the activities provided below will act as a structure for the local implementation of the dissemination strategy, while the stakeholders involved, the targeted audiences and the specific issues to be addressed will be specified for each area, based on the results of the preliminary requirement collection.

B.o.2 Communication activities

Throughout the implementation of each phase specific activities are planned, using a variety of appropriate tools for the specific objectives of the dissemination stream and the engagement of the respective stakeholders.

For the implementation of the local targeted activities a dissemination toolkit with significant flexibility and adjustability is available. This provides partners with the respective freedom to adjust the organised activities thematically in order to best suit the local requirements. More specifically, for each location in which the targeted activities are to take place, the following elements will be taken into account in order to organise the respective activities accordingly:

- Identification and mapping of the main stakeholders involved → stakeholder management activities
- Experience and/ or effectiveness of local environmental & youth organisations → identification of potential co-organisers/ multipliers for synergy building
- The most important environmental issues → specification of the thematic approach of the activities
- Current level of awareness of local stakeholders and especially youth population and respective justification → specification of the scope of the activities (educational, informative, awareness raising, motivational, etc.)

Following the requirement analysis, the next step is to plan the suitable activities for each distinct phase, according to the specific objectives and based on the local needs. The dissemination activities are to take place within each distinct phase, as outlined in previous sections, ensuring successful completion of each phase in order to move on to the next one.

Specifically, for each dissemination stream the activities are planned as follows:

1st Phase: Commitment activities

A core team of experts is to be formed in order to effectively contribute to the necessary knowledge diffusion in fields relevant to the most important local environmental issues and other project related fields (environmental policy, activists, etc.), as well as from the local administrative bodies and organisations. In order to ensure the commitment of at least 5 individuals with relevant expertise, the potential members of the network will be contacted, at first, through direct communication means (telephone-teleconference, person-to-person meetings, interviews, etc.). Next, after a first-level contact with a significant number of persons, a local focus group in each area (Network of Interest) is to be organised, with the participation of representatives of the respective partner (Comune Di Sant' Agata del Bianco, Municipality of Mollet de Valles, Municipality of Valdemoro, Region of Crete, and Municipality of Hatay), in cooperation with the leader of the WP7 in order to develop a common approach in contributing to the project's objectives in the area.

The project partners should effectively communicate the general context of the project, its objectives, actions and expected results in order for the participating parties to be able to act as multipliers within their networks. Also, the participating experts should have a clear view of the project's dissemination strategy, ensuring complementarity with the successive activities.

Indicative timeline:	Months 3 to 15
Specific objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Commitment of at least 5 individuals for every pilot area (experts + project partners’ representatives) to provide expertise and spread knowledge
Milestones:	Organisation of the local Networks of Interest

2nd Phase: Information and Knowledge exchange activities

After ensuring the commitment of the Network of Interest (1st Phase), local workshops will co-organised with the staff of the respective partners, under the coordination and consultation of the WP7 leader. The workshops will be facilitated by the members of the Network and will be open to the wider public, in order to provide dissemination to the general project’s components (objectives, activities, results, etc.). The workshops, through the interaction and discussions among the local stakeholders, should result to the creation of a working-team, consisting of representatives of local authorities, public policy bodies and local organisations, which will coordinate the organisation of participatory activities for local youth (open events – 3rd Phase), within local popular festivities organised on a regular basis.

After each local workshop, at least 3 round tables should be organised in order to capitalise the results of the workshop and to provide effective coordination of the organisation of the targeted activities.

The project team should inform the WP7 leader about:

- the workings and results of the coordination activities (workshop, round tables)
- the people involved in the local working-team
- the proposed local festivities that will be the occasion for the open events.

Indicative timeline:	Months 16 to 20
Specific objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Participation in local workshops – round tables of (per event): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 5 representatives from local authorities ● 10 representatives from local NGOs, citizens groups and active communities ● Creation of 5 local working-groups (one for every pilot area) with local stakeholders (NGOs, communities, cooperatives, etc.) with the project partners for the co-organisation of local participatory events
Milestones:	Completion of local workshops

3rd Phase: Participatory activities

During the third phase the main targeted audience of young men and women is to be approached, with the aim to engage them to a series of participatory open events (fair hunts, festivals, interactive simulation events, etc.). The local working-team (2nd Phase) will prepare a proposal for the organisation of 2-3 open events on local and/ or regional level, within the occasion of local popular festivities.

According to the local requirements, as indicated in the preliminary study and will be further specified within the 1st and 2nd Phase, the concept of the events should:

D7.1: 1st Dissemination Plan

- ◉ thematically match to provide awareness and information on the most important local environmental issues
- ◉ promote collaborative action and inform about the opportunities for participation on local decision making
- ◉ raise awareness regarding local environmental issues
- ◉ have as primary objective the information and mobilisation of local youth
- ◉ be communicated through the appropriate channels to target youth
- ◉ provide effective dissemination of the general project idea, objectives, activities and results.

The final context and specific activities of the events will be decided upon consensus among the local working-team in cooperation with the dissemination leader. Also, necessary for the effectiveness of the activities of the 3rd phase is that the eParticipation platform has been put into pilot operation, in order to engage pilot users and enhance participation in the platform.

Indicative timeline:	Months 20 to 30
Specific objectives:	◉ Organisation of local participatory events
Milestones:	Planning of the concept for 5 participatory events (one in each area)

4th Phase: Feedback and Dissemination activities

The fourth phase includes a set of parallel dissemination activities, targeted on local level, which will provide dissemination for the main project context, objectives, activities and outputs, as well as information and publicity regarding the organisation of local activities (1st, 2nd & 3rd Phase).

Specifically, each partner will be responsible for the following tasks:

- ◉ **Project website – Social Media:** Provide information on regular basis to the WP7 leader for the update of the project website and social media pages.
- ◉ **Press Releases:** Update and integrate the list with local press and mass media and provide performance data to the WP7 leader for the editing of press releases. Also, targeted coverage (interviews, messages, etc.) will be scheduled on local mass media (TV, radio, internet media) within the occasion of upcoming or completed local activities.
- ◉ **Audiovisual material:** Create relevant material from the organisation of local events.
- ◉ **e-mail – Newsletters:** Assist DRAXIS with the development and update of the STEP mailing lists by providing contact information of local stakeholders.
- ◉ **Informational material:** Translate content and develop the relevant material (brochures, conference material, etc.) using the available templates and content in English language
- ◉ **Presentations:** Participation in non-project events for the dissemination of the project's context.

These activities will take place throughout the whole duration of the project, gaining special feedback from the completion of the previous dissemination phases, as well as from the rest of the project activities.

B.o.3 Measurement of success

Activity	Objectives	Tools & Techniques	Outputs	Monitoring
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Informal meetings Interviews Focus groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Commitment of experts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Group decision making techniques Collective intelligence techniques 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Commitment of 5 individuals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Letters of consent
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Workshop 3 Round tables 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information of local interested parties Exchange of knowledge Creation of synergies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Structured dialogue techniques Facilitated working group techniques 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participation of minimum 15 individuals (per event) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants' lists Minutes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engagement of young men and women in participatory action Participation of local youth in eParticipation platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interactive simulation events Thematic festivals Fair hunts/ walk rounds Clean up/ restore events Online/ mobile applications & games Social media campaigns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participation of total 200 participants in each event 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Events' reports Platform user data
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Press releases Newsletters Printed & Audiovisual material Social media & project website Public presentations (Non-project events) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dissemination of project's general context Dissemination of the local activities Dissemination of the participation outcomes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project's Dissemination Plan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 12 press entries on local press Material and recipients for tactical newsletters of the project Development and Distribution of printed material Creation of audiovisual material Material for social media and project website Presentation to at least 1 non-project event 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Copies of entries Mailing list records Copies of material Social network activity Presentation

B.o.3 Collecting Requirements

In order to appropriately plan the targeted dissemination activities in each one of the five pilot areas, a collection of requirements has been elaborated, ensuring the development of a clear view of the existing situation, stakeholders and specific needs and priorities. The collection of requirements has been completed with the use of semi-structured questionnaires, filled-in by 5 distinct partners, covering all 5 pilot areas. The questionnaires were structured as follows:

Part 1: General Information

The first part concerns general information of the partners, which are all public local/ regional government bodies, and their respective areas of jurisdiction. The questions included information such as population and

youth population as well as basic statistics, such as unemployment rates etc. The aim of this part is to capture the basic information of the respective areas, which affect all the other indicators accordingly.

Part 2: Environmental Policy

The second part includes questions regarding the identification and assessment of stakeholders involved in local environmental policy making. Specifically, the partners are required to provide assessment of the impact and influence on environmental policy issues for the following stakeholder groups:

- **Central government bodies**, either acting centrally or on local level, but implementing centrally planned policy
- **Regional/ Local authorities**, bodies of local public administration, either on regional or local level
- **Local businesses**, local SMEs and entrepreneurs, with a strong interest regarding environmental policy
- **Large/ Multinational firms**, locally based corporations (MNCs, etc.) with significant industrial activity, having an impact on the environment
- **Environmental organisations**, active non-profit/ for-benefit organisations (NGOs, Cooperatives, etc.) with highly community-oriented activity and focus on the environment and local issues
- **Citizens**, either as groups of interest or as individuals, interacting through formal or informal channels.

The partners were also asked to specify any other groups not included in the previous groups. Furthermore, the partners were asked to indicate the main public bodies associated with local environmental policy in their areas, specifying their association with the field in focus. Also, an identification of the most crucial local environmental issues and an assessment of the overall effectiveness of the environmental policy making on local level have been drafted.

The following set of questions referred to the local population and the local level of awareness. The focus has been placed on young people in an attempt to identify the level of youth awareness and mobilisation regarding the environment and local environmental policy. Also, the partners were asked to specify the possible reasons for lack of awareness or action motivation of the local youth.

Part 3: Experience – Networking

The third part aimed at mapping the local facilitators and multipliers, the local stakeholders that will be in close cooperation with the project partners in the development of the targeted activities. Also, a preliminary assessment of their level of experience and effectiveness in the field has been attempted, in order to identify possible opportunities or threats that needed to be addressed. Regarding the latter, the participation of the local youth population has also been examined, in order to develop an integrated approach in involving them in future activities.

Part 4: General dissemination strategy

The fourth part was for internal purposes, requesting from the partners to assess the general dissemination strategy, identify possible challenges and make their proposals for successful implementation. The purpose of this part was to enhance the involvement of the partners in the planning of the dissemination strategy, in order to ensure the necessary commitment in its implementation.

B.o.4 Stakeholders management

According to the general outline, different sets of stakeholders are targeted from each dissemination stream. This variation is based on distinct motivation objectives for each specific audience and within each distinct

phase of the strategy. Also, a different approach will be followed for each set of local stakeholders, as grouped in the requirement collection phase. The identified stakeholders will be sorted according to the potential level of involvement in the process of the dissemination activities. The analysis will make use of the stakeholder management matrix in order to map the identified stakeholders according to their:

- **Influence** on local environmental policy
- **Impact** of the relevant stakeholders on the specified issues.

This two-axes approach is graphically represented in a matrix as indicated below:

The above Figure provides a priority classification in ensuring that the right message goes to the right target audience. A stakeholder's position on the grid illustrates particular actions that may be taken in interaction. More specifically:

- **High-influence, high-impact target-groups:** Significant efforts should be made to ensure the active participation of representatives in the project activities
- **High-influence, low-impact target-groups:** Effort should be made to keep this group informed and involved regarding the projects activities. However particular actions aim to enhance the impact of this specific group in cooperation with the high-impact group.
- **Low-influence, high-impact target groups:** This group is adequately informed and close communication is stressed to ensure participation in the project activities. The aim is on the one hand to ensure effective information on the project and its objectives, and participation to its activities, and on the other hand the enhancement of their position in the matrix towards the high-influence quadrant.
- **Low-influence, low-impact individuals:** Monitor members of this group for consideration and consultation or changes in behaviour.

After the completion of a dissemination phase, each targeted audience -targeted as a receiver of the dissemination stream- should act as a transmission pole for the next dissemination stream. Thus, the global objective of the enhancement of participation of the interested parties regarding environmental policy, especially young men and women, is made possible throughout the dissemination process.

Specifically, the main targeted audiences for each phase are as follows:

1. Commitment of the Network of Interest:
 - Experts in the fields of environment & policy making
 - Academia and scientists from relevant fields
 - Representatives of NGOs and Networks with in-depth knowledge in decision making procedures for youth and environment in the region
 - Representatives from relevant civil society organisations, professional associations and European networks - Policy makers
 - Representatives of the project partners, who will act as members of the Executive Board and the General Assembly, as well as members of the working groups of the project.
2. Knowledge Exchange
 - Representatives from local NGOs & active communities
 - Local authorities and policy making stakeholders
 - Local stakeholders from business sector and other fields concerned to environmental policy
 - Local opinion forming groups (local press, journalists, activists, education and training staff, etc.)
 - Individuals with a close involvement in the implementation of the pilot project.
3. Action motivation
 - Young people interested in youth engagement in decision making procedures – especially non-experts
 - Local stakeholders.
4. Feedback & Dissemination
 - Global and local Network of Interest
 - Local stakeholders
 - Local and national authorities and policy making stakeholders
 - General public.

B.1 Context of the dissemination activities in Italy (Comune Di Sant'Agata del Bianco)

B.1.1 Current situation

Sant'Agata del Bianco is a small municipality, member of Locride Municipalities Association in the province of Reggio Calabria. The Locride district has a population of around 130.000, with the significant amount of 24.976 being young men and women (16-30 years old). A significant percentage (30%) of the local youth is university students, while another 22% being post-graduate students. The unemployment rate is at around 25% and 58% for young people. The basic income sources of the area are the tourism sector, agriculture and aquaculture as well as the services sector.

Regarding the local environmental policy, the Central Government as well as local and regional authorities have been designated as the most important in terms of influencing the local decision making, with citizens, local organisations and local businesses having less influence. The most important environmental issues in the area are sea water pollution, litter, solid waste and deterioration of urban environment. Although numerous initiatives have been undertaken for environmental action, the overall environmental policy in the area is deemed from problematic and disoriented to ineffective. The local population seems to be generally informed concerning the above issues; however they are not considered active or sensitised, with the local youth appearing as more indifferent. The latter is being explained by a general lack of involvement of the

young population in the public sphere and decision making procedures, as well as by a lack of confidence for change and a sense of helplessness.

The local population use as main information sources regarding local environmental policy the local press and the internet, along with information delivered by local organisations (local NGOs, Clubs, etc.). Local young people are mainly being informed about local environmental policy issues from the same sources.

In the Locride area there is a large and diverse number of civil society organisations, from local environmental NGOs and youth organisations, to local cultural and sports organisations, as well as active communities and informal groups. The local organisations are characterised by an advanced level of experience in organising and participating in environmental activities, through the implementation of projects fostering the preservation and promotion of the natural environment and its biodiversity, exalting and enhancing local production, recovery craft and the huge cultural heritage. The effectiveness of these actions on the current situation concerning the local issues is regarded to be in positive direction but of little actual effect. The participation of local youth in such actions is limited, with the lack of information and environmental education being designated as the main causes.

The local young population is considered as highly experienced in the use of ICT tools, with the lack of education and training being regarded as the main cause for not using these tools in participatory processes in social and policy related issues.

B.1.2 Target audiences

As indicated by the questionnaires, a diverse set of stakeholders is involved in local environmental policy, in terms of having significant influence in the decision making procedures and regarding the potential impact of the project activities on them. The most important stakeholders recorded are indicated below:

Administrative bodies:

- Regione Calabria – Dipartimento Ambiente e territorio
- Provincia di Reggio Calabria – Settore 14-Ambiente ed energia
- Municipal authorities - 42 Municipalities of Locride area
- Ente Parco dell'Aspromonte

Local organisations:

Organisation	Activity field
Associazione Civitas Solis - www.civitassolis.org	Youth and social work
Forum territoriale terzo settore Locride	Social & networking
Ymca	Sport and youth work
Lados	Social work
Mediterraneo & Ambiente	Environment
Caritas	Social work
Arci Pesca Fisa	Environment
Osservatorio ambientale diritto per la vita	Environment
Sporting Locri	Sport

From the recorded local stakeholders, as grouped for their mapping within the planning of local dissemination strategy, the most significant in influencing the local environmental policy has been indicated the central government bodies, with the local and regional bodies coming next, as well as local environmental organisations. According to this, the strategy regarding the dissemination flow to each stakeholder group is as indicated in the following matrix:

<p>Keep Satisfied</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local businesses 	<p>Manage Closely</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Central Government Regional/ Local authorities
<p>Monitor</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large/ Multinational firms 	<p>Keep Informed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental organisations Citizens

According to the above mapping, the specific objectives for the priority target groups are formed as follows:

- Closely coordinate communications with central government bodies and local authorities, ensuring their involvement in the dissemination activities
- Effectively inform, raise awareness and stimulate local environmental organisations and citizens regarding the environment and environmental policy, aiming to maximise the impact of the dissemination activities on them and in enhancing their position in local decision making
- Keep other local stakeholders informed to provide effective visibility of the project's activities.

B.1.3 Specialisation of the strategy

According to the previous analysis, the planned activities should focus in addressing the main issues regarding the participation of young people in the following manner:

- Engage both central and local actors regarding environmental policy making in the networking and knowledge exchange activities, as well as local environmental organisations and citizens' groups, which appear to have significant experience in organising local activities
- To strengthen the local civil society network and enhance the attraction of the local organisations for young people to participate in activities
- To increase the visibility of local environmental actions and enhance the participation of local youth
- Especially target local youth population in participating in local activities, aiming to raise awareness on local environmental issues
- Enhance activities related to environmental education, through informational activities
- To inform the local youth on the benefits of their involvement in decision making procedures, also using innovative and participatory ICT tools, including the STEP eParticipation platform
- To raise awareness of local authorities on the perspectives of the participation of local young population in increasing the effectiveness of local environmental policy.

The dissemination activities will attempt to build on the current experience of the local organisations, creating and strengthening a network of local stakeholders (organisations, associations, local authorities, experts, etc.) with expertise on issues in focus, significant influence on local environmental policy and experience in organising participatory actions. At the same time, the local youth population will be approached to increase their knowledge on environmental issues, as well as on potential participatory solutions. The enhanced participation of young people in the organised activities will, in turn, create the necessary conditions for a more active involvement of young people in local decision making regarding the environment, thus enhancing the effectiveness of the procedures.

Also, relevance with the pilot scenario should be ensured, regarding the following issues, as drafted in the project's Description of Work:

- development of local policies for re-use, recycling and reduce of waste
- limitation of activities that contribute to the increase of air and water pollution
- renewable forms of energy and sustainable use of local environmental resources.

B.2 Context of the dissemination activities in Spain (Mollet de Valles Municipality & Valdemoro Municipality)

B.2.1 Current situation

In Spain the pilot area covers the Municipality of Mollet de Valles and the Municipality of Valdemoro. Specific requirements have been collected for each one of the two areas.

The Municipality of Mollet de Valles is a small city of the metropolitan area of Barcelona with a population of 51.000 residents, with an average age of 38,5 years old. A significant percentage of around 15% is young population of 16 – 30 years old, with an equal ratio of young men and women. The unemployment rate is at

around 17%, with the respective rate for youth ranging from 14% (25-34 years old) to 29% (16-24 years old). The basic income sources are industry and services.

Regarding environmental policy, it is assumed that the local and regional authorities have the strongest influence on local decision making regarding the environment, with the central government's and business stakeholders' influence being considered as insignificant. Other bodies having adequate influence are environmental organisations and citizens. The overall local environmental policy is being considered to be in correct direction, though with little effect related to the most important issues in the area, namely air pollution and litter/ solid waste. The awareness level of the local population, including youth population, is being considered neutral or indifferent. This attitude is explained by the lack of environmental education. The main information sources are the local media (TV & Radio), local press and the internet, with the latter being the main information source for local youth, along with information acquired from school.

In the area there have been identified several local organisations, active in the fields of sports and culture, as well as active communities (cooperatives, social clubs, etc.); however no organisations with sheer environmental activity have been indicated. The overall level of experience of local organisations in the implementation of environmental activities is being assessed as positive, having also a positive influence regarding local environmental issues. However, the participation of local youth is being indicated as limited, due to lack of personal motivation and/ or environmental education.

Valdemoro City is a municipal district, located in the Southern zone of the autonomous community of Madrid. The city's population is over 75.000 residents with around 17.000 of them being young people (16-30 years old) and a significant number (around 4.000) being university students. The unemployment rate is around 35% with a rate of around 20% of unemployment for young people. The basic income sources are the industry and the services sectors.

All local stakeholder groups identified (central government, regional/ local authorities, local businesses, large/ multinational firms, environmental organisations and citizens) are being considered to have a significant influence on local environmental policy, with the most significant being national and local authorities and citizens. The most important environmental issues in the area are considered to be air pollution, the deterioration of urban environment and lack of urban green area, with the local environmental policy being regarded to be in positive direction but with little effect. A relative high level of awareness is indicated in the local population, including youth population. Regarding any relevant lack of awareness about the local environmental issues, as main cause is regarded the lack of personal motivation, while environmental education at schools is being considered positive. The main information sources are the local media and the internet, with the latter being the main information source for youth.

Several organisations have been identified in the Municipality of Valdemoro as well, mainly in the fields of youth, including a local sports club and a local environmental NGO. The overall experience in local action is being considered as positive, with an also positive effectiveness. The participation of young people in the above activities has been indicated as balanced, indicating partial interest from the majority of the local youth. The relevant lack of interest is being explained to be due to a lack of personal motivation.

B.2.2 Target audiences

The main targeted audiences indicated in the two pilot areas are presented below:

Public/ Administrative bodies:

<u>Mollet des Valles Municipality</u>	<u>Valdemoro Municipality</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Council of Barcelona province 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Casa de la juventud valdemoro
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Agency of waste management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ AFS Intercultura España (volunteer group)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Network of cities and towns towards sustainability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Consejo de la juventud
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Government of Catalonia (department of territory and sustainability) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Asociación de Iniciativas para el Bienestar de los Animales (A.I.B.A.). - valdemoro-
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Gallecs Consortium 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ecologistas en Acción Espartal de Valdemoro
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Besos Consortium 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Council of Barcelona province 	

Local organisations:Mollet des Valles Municipality

Organisation	Activity field
Esplai Xivarri	Education and Youth
Club Muntanyenc	Sports and nature
Agroecological Association of Gallecs	Organic agriculture, nature and local production

Valdemoro Municipality

Organisation	Activity field
Las Secuoyas	Youth
Valdemoro Joven	Youth
Escuela de Futbol	Sport
Ecologistas en Acción El Espartal	Environment

Regarding the influence and impact of the stakeholders on the local environmental policy, the situation appears to be quite different in the two areas. The common characteristic is the strong influence of the local stakeholders (local authorities, local organisations and citizens), while the influence of the rest stakeholder groups vary. The two graphics below indicate this difference regarding the stakeholder groups:

D7.1: 1st Dissemination Plan

Following to that, the approach of the dissemination strategy for each one of the two areas is presented in the two matrixes below:

Stakeholder matrix – Mollet de Valles:

Keep Satisfied	Manage Closely
-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Regional/ Local authorities ▪ Citizens
Monitor	Keep Informed
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Central Government ▪ Large/ Multinational firms ▪ Local businesses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Environmental organisations

Stakeholder matrix – Valdemoro:

<p>Keep Satisfied</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Central Government ▪ Large/ Multinational firms 	<p>Manage Closely</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Regional/ Local authorities ▪ Citizens
<p>Monitor</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Local businesses 	<p>Keep Informed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Environmental organisations

From the above, the dissemination strategy activities for both areas share the following common elements:

- Closely coordinate the communications with local authorities and citizens’ groups, ensuring their involvement in the dissemination activities
- Effectively inform and raise awareness of local environmental organisations and citizens, aiming to increase their effectiveness of participation on local environmental policy, through the enhanced cooperation with the high-impact groups
- Provide adequate information to the relevant national government bodies and large corporations ensuring that no barriers are being raised
- Keep other local stakeholders informed to provide effective visibility of the project’s activities.

B.2.3 Specialisation of the strategy

Both pilot areas in Spain appear to share several common characteristics, as regards the local environmental policy and the participation of young people. Local administrative bodies, as well as local organisations and citizens groups are considered to have a strong influence on local environmental policy; however the local youth appears to be unmotivated to participate in relevant activities. Thus, the activities in the context of the local dissemination strategy in the two Spanish areas should be formed taking into account the following:

- A strong influence of local actors is indicated, which should be particularly targeted in promoting youth participation
- The current active civil society network should be strengthened and local coalitions for joint activities between local authorities and civil society organisations, targeted for young people should be facilitated. Examples of participatory management of public spaces and smart-cities initiatives, such as community gardens, including the use of open ICT tools, could provide effective demonstration within the open events.
- The level of awareness of local youth on local decision making should be raised, through alternative means and tools, also promoting their engagement in local organisations and their activities
- Environmental education should be integrated so as to promote participatory activity and include innovative ICT tools.

The message to be communicated is twofold: local environmental policy stakeholders, appearing to be of great significance, should be aware of the value added from the participation of young people, while young people should be aware of the positive impact that this participation may have on them and their area.

Also, the activities should integrate the specific issues and cases as indicated in the draft pilot scenarios, outlined in the project's Description of Work, namely:

Mollet de Valles:

- air pollution reduction
- creation of more green spaces in the city centre
- sustainable use of environmental resources and management of protected areas located in the Municipality
- recycling
- energy efficiency both in public and private buildings.

Valdemoro:

- creation of green spaces
- efficient use of environmental resources
- sustainable management of protected park next to the city (Parque Regional del Sureste)
- promotion of green transport (e.g. bicycles) and pressure to institutions for relevant infrastructures .

B.3 Context of the dissemination activities in Greece (Region of Crete)

B.3.1 Current situation

The Region of Crete is a second grade local self-government, responsible for designing, planning and implementing of policies at regional level. The population of the region is around 620.000 residents, with a large youth population of almost 110.000 young men and women. In the region there are 2 Universities (University of Crete and Technical University of Crete), with around 20.000 students. The unemployment rate in the region is 21% and for young people it ranges from 28% (25-34 years old) to 51% (15-24 years old). The main income sources are tourism, agriculture and services.

Regarding the regional environmental policy, it appears that the central government bodies have a greater influence than regional and local authorities. Environmental organisations hold an important role with the role of citizens and other stakeholders being relatively restrained. The overall environmental policy appears

to be in the correct direction, however with little effect regarding the main environmental issues of the region, and specifically litter/ solid waste, mixed land use, lack of urban green areas and desertification danger in specific areas, as well as coast erosion. A general lack of long-term sustainable planning is indicated, which further decreases the effectiveness of the various environmental measures taken. The local population appears as unmotivated regarding local environmental issues, with the same attitude being observed to local youth as well. The above attitude is explained due to the lack of personal motivation, as well as the lack of environmental education. The local population uses as information sources mainly the local media and press, while young people prefer the internet and first-hand information from local organisations and school.

Several environmental and youth organisations have been identified with significant activity on regional level, while a large number of local clubs (sport clubs, cultural organisations, etc.) are active in the large cities of Crete. Also, numerous formal and informal groups have adequate action on local level, such as school students clubs, scouts, university clubs, etc. Despite the large number of citizen groups, environmental activity on local level is either completely absent or ineffective. The participation of local young people is also limited, which is explained from the general absence of organised social activities and ineffective visibility of the ones implemented, as well as from the lack of personal motivation and lack of environmental education of the young people. It is regarded that the local youth population has a general lack of interest regarding environmental issues.

B.3.2 Target audiences

A diverse set of local stakeholders is indicated by the questionnaires, including public governing and administrative bodies on local, regional and national level, as well as several organisations:

Public/ Administrative bodies:

- Ministry of Productive Defragmentation, Environment and Energy
- Decentralised Administration of Crete
- Region of Crete, Directorates for Environment and Spatial Planning, for Agricultural Economy, for Development, for Transport and Communication.
- Local Municipalities
- University of Crete, Natural History Museum of Crete, Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (Crete), Technical University of Crete.

Local organisations:

- “Ecocrete” network (umbrella organisation) (www.ecocrete.gr)
- Local sports clubs in every large city of Crete
- Local cultural organisations in villages
- Informal groups (scouts, university students clubs, etc.).

The influence and impact on the local environmental policy is indicated in the figure below:

The crucial role of the central government on local decision making procedures regarding the environment should be noted, while on local level regional/ local authorities and environmental organisations appear to be of greater significance. The stakeholder matrix for the Region of Crete is formed as follows:

<p>Keep Satisfied</p> <p>-</p>	<p>Manage Closely</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Central Government ▪ Regional/ Local authorities ▪ Environmental organisations
<p>Monitor</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Large/ Multinational firms ▪ Local businesses 	<p>Keep Informed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Citizens

According to the above mapping, the specific objectives for the priority target groups are formed as follows:

- Closely coordinate communications with central government bodies and local authorities, ensuring their involvement in the dissemination activities
- Effectively engage local environmental organisations, aiming to maximise their cooperation with the administrative bodies
- Raise public awareness to enhance the participation of citizens, especially youth, in the dissemination activities, aiming to increase their influence on local policy
- Monitor other stakeholders and provide adequate visibility of the project's activities.

B.3.3 Specialisation of the strategy

Limited civil activity and youth participation in the Region of Crete falls within the general absence of public participation in decision making procedures from the majority of stakeholders and the citizens as well. Great attention should be given to young people and the alteration of their attitude. By changing the attitude of young people and enhancing their participation in policy making, society will have much more responsible citizens. Issues on local scale and problems which are easily perceived in everyday life are ideal to trigger the participation of youth. Environmental protection in a local level could act as an initial motivation for young people to participate on collective activities, thus forming the requirements for a more active youth citizenry on local and regional level.

The above should be addressed through the local dissemination activities, especially targeting the following:

- Awareness raising of the local population, especially local youth, on local environmental issues and enhancing the visibility, outreach and effectiveness of local environmental education activities, through informational events
- Information for the local youth on involvement in decision making procedures, also using innovative and participatory ICT tools, valorising the experience from the recent e-government solutions, such as Diavgeia and OpenGov
- Strengthening of the local organisations in planning and implementing local actions and increasing their attractiveness for young people to participate in activities
- Coordinating activities of local scattered clubs and organisations to effectively promote youth participation on local environmental policy, also through jointly organised activities with local authorities
- Increasing the visibility of local environmental actions and enhancing of the participation of local youth
- Promoting the role of local authorities in addressing local challenges with the participation of the local population
- Awareness raising of local authorities on the perspectives of the participation of local young population in increasing the effectiveness of local environmental policy.

Also, the context of the activities should take into account the pilot scenario for the Region of Crete, as drafted in the project's Description of Work, including:

- management of large investments and large scale activities in the Natura 2000 areas
- reduction of uncontrolled waste disposal
- promoting energy efficiency, climate change, environmental risks and causes for natural disasters
- promoting marine spatial planning, integrated coastal zone management.

B.4 Context to the dissemination activities in Turkey (Hatay Metropolitan Municipality)

B.4.1 Current situation

Hatay is one of the biggest cities in the Mediterranean region of Turkey with a population of around 1,5 million residents and 12 districts, while youth population is estimated around 450.000 (16-30 years old). Almost 57.000 people are unemployed, with around 16.000 of which being young people. The main income sources of the area are industry, agriculture/ aquaculture and trade (imports/ exports).

The most significant stakeholders influencing local environmental policy are the local administration bodies (regional/ local authorities), as well as environmental organisations. The influence of the central government is regarded of lesser importance, and even lesser the one of citizens, local businesses and large/ multinational firms. Hatay is facing the most common environmental challenges of large urban areas, such as air and water pollution; however, the most important environmental problem is considered to be the lack of long-term sustainable planning, while the local environmental policy is overall regarded as problematic and disoriented. The local population appears to be well informed about the local environmental problems and sensitised; however young people seem unmotivated, which is explained due to the lack and/ or the ineffectiveness of environmental education. The main information source for the local population are the local media (TV and Radio), while youth population prefers various networks as main information sources.

Several organisations are active in the area, regarding environmental protection and policy; however, overall there appears to be a lack of experience and relative ineffectiveness in the organisation of local environmental actions. The participation of young people in such activities is characterised as limited, which appears to be a consequence of ineffective dissemination of previous experience, from the side of the organisations.

B.4.2 Target audiences

The main targeted audiences identified are listed below:

Public/ Administrative Bodies:

- State Hydraulic Works Republic of Turkey (sea water pollution)
- Hatay Province Directorate of Environment and Urbanism (urban green areas)
- Hatay Province Directorate of Food Agriculture and Livestock (soil pollution)
- Hatay Metropolitan Municipality Department of Environmental Protection.

Local organisations:

Organisation	Activity field
DOĞADER-Nature and Environmental Protection Associations	Environmental protection
Solution Suggestions Symposium on Environmental Issues of Hatay	Create platforms for Environmental Issues
Environmental Protection Agency of Hatay	Environmental protection
Art and Nature Tourism Association of Hatay	Environmental protection
The Nature Conservation Association of Hatay	Environmental protection and Environmental protection

The influence of the local stakeholders on local environmental policy, grouped in 5 categories, is presented in the figure below, in relevance with their potential impact:

The significant influence of the regional/ local authorities and environmental organisations is obvious, while citizens who appear to have the highest impact have restrained influence in decision making. Accordingly, the communication approach is being formed as indicated in the matrix below:

<p>Keep Satisfied</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional/ Local authorities Central Government 	<p>Manage Closely</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental organisations
<p>Monitor</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large/ Multinational firms Local businesses 	<p>Keep Informed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Citizens

The communication objectives for each target group are formed as follows:

- Closely coordinate communication with environmental organisations, aiming to optimise their approach and enhance the level of knowledge on environmental issues and expertise in planning and implementing participatory activities
- Ensure a constant information flow towards the wider public, targeted to young people, to raise awareness and promote their involvement in local decision making
- Provide adequate information to regional/ local as well as central actors regarding policy making to ensure their support in the planned activities
- Monitor the rest local stakeholders for change in behaviour and provide information accordingly.

B.4.3 Specialisation of the strategy

The main issue of long-term sustainable planning in local environmental policy should be seen as an opportunity for the involvement of all the relevant stakeholders in interaction to increase the effectiveness

and consistency of the local policy measures. The enhanced awareness and deeper understanding of local young people regarding local environmental issues and the way they affect them should provide adequate motivation for them to be engaged in participatory activities, which in turn would provide them with the means to increase their influence on local policy making. Therefore, the organisation of the local activities should include the following elements:

- Active engagement of local civil stakeholders in structured dialogue with the main actors influencing the local environmental policy, enhancing their involvement in long-term sustainable planning of environmental policy and strengthen cooperation with local authorities
- Enhance local organisations in successfully plan and implement environmental actions and effectively communicate their statute and activity to attract young people to participate
- Provide motivation for local population, focusing on youth, to be involved in participatory activities on local level
- Promote the integration of ICT tools in planning and implementation of environmental policy, in a manner to involve more stakeholders (citizens, organisations, etc.), as well as a means to increase its effectiveness.

ANNEX C – NEWSLETTER TEMPLATE

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Suspendisse sodales sem a turpis eleifend viverra. Nulla blandit ligula nec aliquam sagittis. Duis fringilla sem neque, id efficitur nibh porta eget. Aliquam erat volutpat. Maecenas vulputate laoreet mollis. Aliquam nec feugiat eros. Pellentesque habitant morbi tristique senectus et netus et malesuada fames ac turpis egestas. Ut convallis ullamcorper malesuada.

Curabitur at viverra enim, eu fringilla tellus. Pellentesque a libero est. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Suspendisse sodales sem a turpis eleifend viverra. Nulla blandit ligula nec aliquam sagittis. Duis fringilla sem neque, id efficitur nibh porta eget. Aliquam erat volutpat. Maecenas vulputate laoreet mollis.

Curabitur at viverra enim, eu fringilla tellus. Pellentesque a libero est. Fusce tempor velit id nulla molestie, sed luctus augue venenatis. Fusce gravida purus vel porttitor pulvinar.

Curabitur at viverra enim, eu fringilla tellus. Pellentesque a libero est. Fusce tempor velit id nulla molestie, sed luctus augue venenatis. Fusce gravida purus vel porttitor pulvinar. Quisque tempor nunc at risus interdum lacinia. Nulla nec placerat lacus, id semper velit. Nulla eu massa fringilla, ornare tortor ut, pellentesque leo.

Proin vehicula nulla dui, eu varius orci laoreet sit amet. Cras placerat in purus ac dictum. Aenean laoreet augue mi, id condimentum libero ullamcorper non. Nunc feugiat faucibus ante, sit amet facilisis sapien. Nunc sit amet risus porta, ultricies neque nec, faucibus enim. Suspendisse dignissim dapibus faucibus. Mauris lacinia augue cursus congue venenatis.

In viverra dolor risus, sed fermentum ligula sollicitudin quis. Sed quis egestas purus, tempor pellentesque dui. Nunc a egestas felis. Curabitur vitae accumsan ante. Ut ac euismod elit, sit amet commodo tortor. Quisque posuere sapien velit, a fringilla velit imperdiet at. Mauris a vulputate neque.

Vestibulum ornare mollis suscipit. Interdum et malesuada fames ac ante ipsum primis in faucibus. Pellentesque vitae tortor ac dolor ultrices laoreet vel in sem. Integer facilisis tellus ut lectus lacinia, nec aliquam lorem ultricies. Vestibulum pulvinar nulla viverra est porta dictum nec at erat.

Horizon 2020
European Union's
research and innovation
programme

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493.

This publication has been produced with the assistance of the European Union. The contents of this publication is the sole responsibility of DRAXIS and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Union.

ANNEX D – STEP LEAFLET

ANNEX E – MASS MEDIA & NEWS AGENCIES

Country	Media	Link
Greece	Athens – Macedonian News Agency	www.amna.gr
	Cretan News Agency	www.cna.gr
	Evropaiki Ekfrasi	www.ekfrasi.gr
	European Commission press office in Greece	http://ec.europa.eu/greece/index_el.htm
	Athens Photo News	www.apn.gr
Germany	Holsteiner Courier	www.shz.de

D7.1: 1st Dissemination Plan

	Morgenpost	www.mopo.de
	Der Spiegel	www.spiegel.de
	Die Welt	www.welt.de
	Süddeutsche Zeitung	www.sueddeutsche.de
	Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung	www.faz.net
	taz die tageszeitung	www.taz.de
	Die Zeit	www.zeit.de
	Greenpeace Magazin	www.greenpeace-magazin.de
	natur - Magazin für Natur, Umwelt und besseres Leben	www.natur.de
United Kingdom	The Courier (local newspaper)	www.thecourier.co.uk
	The Guardian (national newspaper)	http://www.theguardian.com/uk-news
	Green Futures Magazine	http://forumforthefuture.org/greenfutures
	Environmental Technology	www.envirotech-online.com
Spain	Semanal de Valdemoro (printed and digital edition; reaching 25.000 families in the area)	http://www.valdemoro.es/semanal.es
	Gente Digital	http://www.gentedigital.es/valdemoro/
	SER Radio Chain	
	COPE Radio Chain	
	El 9Nou - regional level	
	Contrapunt -local level	
	Línia Vallès -regional level	
	Mollet a mà- local level	
	El Periódico -regional level	
	La Vanguardia -national level	
	El País -national level	
Turkey	HRT- Hatay radio and television channel	
	Hatay Life	
	Hatay newspaper	
	TRT-Turkish Radio and	

	Television Channel	
	Anadolu Agency	
	Mainstream Media	
Italy	Agenzia Italia	www.agenziaitalia.it
	Agenzia Italiana di Informazione	www.ansa.it
	Corriere della Serra	www.corriere.it
	La Repubblica	www.repubblica.it
Czech Republic	Czech News Agency	www.ctk.eu
	Prague Post	www.praguepost.com
	Ceske Noviny	www.ceskenoviny.cz
	Mladá fronta Dnes	www.idnes.cz
	The Prague Daily Monitor	www.praguemonitor.com
Sweden	TT News Agency	http://info.tt.se/
	The Local	www.thelocal.se
	All Over Press	www.alloverpress.se

ANNEX F – RELEVANT JOURNALS

Scientific Journals
Government Information Quarterly (<i>IT Management, Policies, and Practice</i>)
Telecommunications Policy (<i>ICT Economy, Governance and Society</i>)
Telematics and Informatics (<i>Social impacts of New Technologies</i>)
Technological Forecasting and Social Change
Information and Management
Computers in Human Behaviour
Environmental Sociology
Journal of Environmental Psychology
Computers, Environment & Urban Systems
Environment & Behaviour

European Journal of eParticipation
Environment and Natural Resources Journal
Eco World (<i>Ecology and economy</i>)
UmweltMagazin (<i>Environmental technology & management</i>)
Umwelt aktuell (<i>Latest developments in environmental policy in Germany and EU</i>)
Wirtschaft & Umwelt (<i>Ecology & environmental policy</i>)
Deutsche Jugend (<i>Youth policies</i>)

ANNEX G – TARGETED EVENTS

Event	Description	Location / period
IFIP EGOV 2015	eGovernment & eParticipation	Thessaloniki, Greece/ September 2015
Rockwave Festival	Rock music festival that attracts million of young people	Athens, Greece/ July 2016
Athens Food Festival	Food Festival	Athens, Greece/ Spring 2016
Thessaloniki International Film Festival	Large film festival that attracts hundreds of young people around the world	Thessaloniki, Greece/ Annual event
Thessaloniki Documentary Festival	Large documentary festival that attracts hundreds of young people around the world	Thessaloniki, Greece/ Annual event
In-Edit	International Music Documentary Film Festival	Greece/ Annual event
Panhellenic Festival of Thessaloniki	Popular Book Festival in Greece	Thessaloniki, Greece/ Annual event
CHI 2016	Premier Human Computer Interaction conference	California/ May 2016
British HCI 2016	Human Computer Interaction conference	UK/ July 2016
CeDEM16	International Conference for E-Democracy	Austria/ May

D7.1: 1st Dissemination Plan

	and Open Government	2016
ICDGS 2016	International Conference on e-Democracy, e-Government and e-Society	Paris/ January 2016
Ciclo de Conferencias Open Government: ICT & Justice	ICT in Justice and Public Administration	Annual meeting
Valdemoro Festivities	Festival that gathers young people from Valdemoro and surrounding towns/cities, with special activities dedicated to young people	Valdemoro, Spain/ September 2015
Green Cities and sustainability	Forum in green cities innovation/ Presentation of successful use cases	Malaga, Spain/ October 2015
ECOFIRA (EGETICA & EFIAQUA)	Efficient management of environment and water forum for public administrations and ICT	Valencia, Spain/ October 2015
Valdemoro Spring Festivities	Festival that gathers young people from Valdemoro and surrounding towns/cities, with special activities dedicated to young people	Valdemoro, Spain/ May 2016
Artisans' Fair	Exhibition and sales of handicraft products – 50.000 visitors	Old Town - Mollet del Vallès, Spain/ September 2015
Winter City Festival: Sant Vicenç	Large festival that attracts a lot of young people	Mollet del Vallès, Spain/ Annual event
Summer City Festival	Large festival that attracts a lot of young people	Mollet del Vallès, Spain/ Annual event
Spring festival	Environmental workshops	Barcelona, Spain/ Annual event
Gallecs' Festival	Promotion of agricultural products and eco-cultural activities	Barcelona, Spain/ Annual event
Gallecs' Fairs	Promotion of agricultural products of Galleces	Barcelona, Spain/ Annual event
Mollet Fair	Weekly thematic fairs	Mollet del Vallès, Spain/ Annual event
Tree Festival	Trees afforestation performed by citizens	Mollet del Vallès, Spain/ Annual

D7.1: 1st Dissemination Plan

	(around 400 yearly)	event
Spring Festival for university students	Music festival that attracts million of young people	Hatay, Turkey/ May 2016
Hatay Youth Festival	Music festival that attracts million of young people	Hatay, Turkey/ May 2016
Hot soup support for university students	Municipality's initiative within the scope of supporting young people	Hatay, Turkey/ September 2016- June 2017
Rock'n Coke Festival	Rock music festival that attracts million of young people	Istanbul, Turkey/ Annual event
Istanbul Independent Film Festival	Independent film festival	Istanbul, Turkey/ February 2016
Technology Awards Festival	Technology festival at which individuals and institutions are awarded for their contribution to social life	Istanbul, Turkey/ May 2016
World Intelligent Cities Summit	An international event related to smart cities and technology. High-level decision makers and professionals attends this event.	Istanbul, Turkey/ December 2015
Rock am Ring 2016	One of the largest youth music festivals in Germany wiht lots of livebands on 4 stages	Mending, Germany/ June 2016
YOU Berlin 2016	YOU Berlin is one of the leading trade show for youth culture and is divided into the two segments "music.sports.lifestyle." and "education. Carrer. future.".	Berlin, Germany/ July 2016
Green Days 2015	Environmental ideas networking for young people	Vienna, Austria/ September 2015
EYE 2016 (=European Youth Event)	The European Parliament in Strasbourg is opening its doors to thousands of young Europeans, who will have a unique opportunity to meet and discuss with European decision-makers. As the event's motto is "Together we can make a change", participants are also encouraged to come up with their own ideas for how to improve Europe.	Strasbourg, France/ May 2016

ANNEX H – REPORTING TEMPLATES

This annex includes the reporting templates for: a) dissemination publications, and b) dissemination events. All partners are required to send information on all dissemination publications and events to the WP7 leader using these templates.

H1 Template for Reporting Dissemination Publications

Date	DD/MM/YY
Task	Which dissemination activity does this publication belong to?
Description	Type of publication/ published where/ title of article
Estimated Reach	Number of people the activity has reached
Target Audience	Describe the type of audience this activity has reached
Partners involved	Partner acronym
Results	Did you receive any response? Was the story picked up somewhere else?
Link	If the publication/article is online, please provide a link

H2 Template for Reporting Dissemination Events

Event title, place, dates	Seminar/ infoday/ bilateral meeting/ fair trade/ stand City, Country DD/MM/YY
Event aim & purpose	Write 2-4 lines to describe the objectives of the event and link to the project objectives
Impact to the project	Write 2-4 lines about the impact of such an activity to the project, e.g. create awareness about the project's outcomes, encourage involvement, create synergies with organisations or projects, collaboration agreements with third existing parties, strengthen links with public bodies, consolidate exploitation position, etc.
Type of audience	Write the type of audience that attended the event
Target audience reached	Write the type of audience that you reached during the event
Size of audience	Write the number of all people that attended the event
Coverage Level	Local/ regional/ national/ European level

Partners involved	Partner acronym
-------------------	-----------------

Brief report and feedback gathered

- Write 1-2 lines to describe the content and the goal of your presentation/presence
e.g. Content: present project introduction
e.g. Goal: increase public visibility, stakeholders attraction and involvement, etc.
- Write 2 or more lines for any comment you received from the audience that you consider useful and explain how the consortium should utilise this
- Write 1-2 lines about a follow-up / post-meeting you have arranged with any stakeholder